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CHRONIC HEPATITIS B GUIDELINE ADHERENCE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2016

ABSTRACT

Asians have the highest prevalence of all ethnic groups as chronic carriers of hepatitis B but up to 50% of healthcare providers fail to properly manage the disease. This study summarized existing knowledge and comprehensively evaluated provider nonadherence to the chronic hepatitis B (CHB) guidelines in Asian Americans. A systematic literature review was conducted utilizing the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) framework. A search was performed in PubMed, CINAHL (the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature), and Cochrane databases from January 2006 to January 2016. Only primary studies that evaluated provider adherence to hepatitis B treatment guidelines were included. Foreign studies outside the United and non-English articles were excluded. Studies that did not evaluate nonadherence were also excluded. Only 14 studies were identified that met the inclusion criteria for this review. These studies consisted of 6 surveys of providers' knowledge and/or attitudes, 6 retrospective chart reviews, and 2 mixed methods.

All included studies evaluated provider adherence to CHB management with respect to four areas: (a) timely routine laboratory checks, (b) treatment initiation when indicated, (c) liver biopsy, and (d) hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) screening. One investigator screened the titles and abstracts of each article. From the included studies, barriers were abstracted via a thematic analysis. A framework for guideline adherence was constructed based on the health belief model.

A total of 35 barriers were categorized into 6 health-belief-model-based themes: (a) self-efficacy (lack of knowledge, unfamiliarity, or unawareness), (b) perceived barriers (patient culture, language, reluctance, or beliefs), (c) perceived severity (factors associated with routine labs and treatment), (d) perceived susceptibility (factors associated with HCC screening), (e) perceived benefits (confidence in the guidelines), and (f) modifying factors (demographics, attitudes, sociopsychological factors). This review highlights the primary barriers to provider adherence to guidelines and offers suggestions and a framework for further research.

In this project, treatment disparity was evaluated from an atypical perspective, placing the burden of disease management on providers. The CHB adherence framework provides a foundation for future models on nonadherence from a behavioral and psychosocial standpoint. Providers can evaluate their current practices and improve their management of CHB with the use of this framework.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you to my family and friends for their continuous support. Also, I am grateful for the guidance of Dr. Ayman Tailakh and Dr. Feng-Ping Lee, who are also the guarantors of this review.

Due to time limitations, this review was not registered in the national registry of PROSPERO and no registration number is available. This is not an amendment of a previously published protocol.

No financial resources or funded sponsors were provided to the completion of this review.

BACKGROUND

The prevalence of hepatitis B infection has rapidly grown in Asian countries due to the lack of standard vaccination procedures, vertical transmission, and other risk factors (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2007). In many Asian countries, such as Vietnam, up to 30% of the inhabitants harbor the virus (Nebbia, Peppia, & Maini, 2012). Among this population, the lifetime risk of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is greater than 60%; most infections are acquired at birth or during early childhood, when the risk of developing chronic infections is greatest (Te & Jensen, 2010).

Approximately 1%-20% of immigrants born in foreign countries are chronic HBV carriers, with rates much higher from Asia (Te & Jensen, 2010). Virtually 70% of patients with acute hepatitis B have subclinical hepatitis. The remaining 30% develop icteric hepatitis (Liaw et al., 1998). Progression from acute to chronic hepatitis is largely dependent on the individual's age when acquiring the infection. Neonates who acquire the infection at birth have a 90% chance of progressing to chronic hepatitis B (CHB) infection (Beasley et al., 1982). Adults have less than 5% chance of progression to CHB infection (Tassopoulos et al., 1987).

Persistent CHB infection complicates to numerous sequelae including hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and increases mortality in chronic carriers (Fattovich, Bortolotti, & Donato, 2008). Tong et al. (2009) established that 4.4% of patients developed HCC after being diagnosed with cirrhosis. In these patients, 23% will decompensate within 5 years. Persistently high serum viral counts were an independent predictor of development of HCC over time. Even patients with undetectable hepatitis B

surface antigen or DNA viral loads had a significantly increased risk of HCC if they had an isolated hepatitis B core antibody (H. C. Kim et al., 2004).

In the United States, 800,000 to 1.4 million people are infected, leading to mortality rates of 2,000-4,000 per year (Fattovich et al., 2008). Te and Jensen (2010) reported nearly half of individuals infected with HBV live in “China, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, sub-Saharan Africa, Pacific Islands, parts of the Middle East, and the Amazon Basin” (p. 2). The CDC (2007) emphasized that chronic HBV infection can have potentially serious consequences including liver failure, liver damage, and HCC. HCC is associated with significant mortality, with a 5-year death rate ranging from 34% to 98% (Yuen et al., 2005). CHB guidelines exist to establish methods for treating disease and preventing the progression to life-threatening liver complications (Tong, Hsu, Chang, & Blatt, 2011). Many gastroenterology and liver specialists worldwide established these guidelines to direct providers when managing patients with CHB.

Problem Statement

Numerous clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) from various medical societies have been published to guide healthcare providers in managing and treating patients with CHB (Liaw et al., 2008; Lok & McMahon, 2009). The Asian Pacific Association for the Study of Liver (APASL), European Association for the Study of the Liver (EASL), U.S. Panel, and the Association for the Study of Liver Diseases (AASLD) are the mainstay societal guidelines for CHB management (EASL, 2012). There are four areas for proper management of CHB: (a) monitoring labs on a timely basis, (b) ordering liver biopsy to guide management, (c) screening for HCC, and (d) starting treatment when indicated. Lack of adherence is defined as failure in any area of the CPGs. Despite widespread

dissemination of numerous guidelines, there is a failure to properly monitor and initiate treatment in 50% of patients who are treatment eligible (Zhang et al., 2012). One study in San Francisco demonstrated that less than one third of patients with CHB were referred to a specialist for proper treatment (CDC, 2007). Multiple studies have demonstrated that there is a lack of adherence to treatment guidelines (L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Ku et al., 2013). These studies validated that there was a significant failure to properly manage patients with CHB infections. Despite numerous studies indicating a significant failure for proper disease management, no systematic review has been conducted to comprehensively evaluate the causes and propose a possible solution to improve adherence to the CHB management guidelines among healthcare providers in the United States.

Purpose Statement

The majority of the studies to evaluate treatment adherence to CHB guidelines are retrospective studies. These studies revealed possible reasons to explain the failure to proper disease monitoring and initiating treatment for treatment-eligible patients (Zhang et al., 2012). Healthcare providers are responsible for timely disease monitoring in CHB patients and starting treatment when appropriate. Although CHB is a major public health problem that is associated with high mortality and morbidity rates, limited data on lack of adherence among healthcare providers exist. A recent search did not reveal any current published literature review on provider nonadherence to the CHB management guidelines. Thus, the purpose of this project was to summarize existing knowledge, comprehensively evaluate provider nonadherence to CHB management guidelines in the

United States, and propose a framework to improve adherence. In addition, areas for future research and interventions will be identified.

Project Aim

This project's aim was to investigate the adherence to CHB guidelines by providers on Asian Americans. This project offered a differential diagnosis to explain why providers may deviate from the recommended practice guidelines and proposed a solution to this problem.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework provides predictions and explanations on relationships between variables in research. Through the process of induction, theories can be modified to explain new phenomena and relationships. The conceptual framework guides the investigator to structure the concepts to provide a systematic approach to answering the project question (Polit & Beck, 2012).

Two supporting frameworks were incorporated into this project. The health belief model (HBM) and the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses protocols (PRISMA-P) statement were incorporated in this review. Evaluation of provider adherence to CHB treatment using the HBM explicated factors for nonadherence. The HBM provided the structure for developing a framework with the purpose of improving provider adherence to CHB treatment recommendations. The study selection process and systematic review protocol was guided by the PRISMA-P.

Literature Review of Theory

A literature review was conducted for prior studies that utilized the HBM for evaluating provider adherence to CHB guidelines. No existing published articles were

available, but Drazic, Caltabiano, and Clough (2012) successfully modified the HBM for developing health-promoting interventions. Maxwell et al. (2014) also modified the HBM to construct a health belief intervention framework that guided their research to develop culturally sensitive interventions.

Drazic et al. (2012) constructed a new framework, the chronic infectious diseases action model (CIDAM), based on the health behavior framework (HBF), and the extended parallel process model (EPPM). The CIDAM is comprised of constructs from the HBM and the EPPM to enhance the predictive capabilities for human behavior. The concepts incorporated into the CIDAM encourage proper messaging and effective communication to promote patient adherence (Drazic et al., 2012).

The EPPM model has constructs that are similar to the HBM. Drazic et al. (2012) added demographics variables, individual factors, and healthcare factors that would individualize and enable the “development of assessment tools and interventions” (p. 1). The construct of healthcare factors consists of “provider factors and medical-social self-efficacy” (Drazic et al., 2012, p. 1). The HBM was revised in a similar fashion to accommodate the factors that may predict provider adherence behaviors to CHB treatment guidelines.

The study by Maxwell et al. (2014) incorporated the HBF to develop culturally sensitive interventions in Asians. The constructs of the HBF are largely similar to the HBM. These similar constructs are perceived severity, perceived susceptibility, perceived benefits, and perceived barriers (Maxwell et al., 2014). The authors developed “theory-based promotion interventions” based on the HBF to help them comprehend concepts that are crucial to modifying behavior (p. 1). The authors conducted a literature

review in concordance with the concepts of the HBF addressing hepatitis B testing (Maxwell et al., 2014). Subsequently, culturally specific interventions were developed on the basis of the constructs from the HBF.

Modifying the HBM

Similar to the development of the CIDAM, the HBM was revised appropriately for the purpose of this project. In addition, the HBM was employed for the development of a framework for this project on a similar level to how Maxwell et al. (2014) adopted the HBF for their instrument. Specifically, the HBM and its six constructs were altered from being patient centered to being specific to the provider.

Perceived severity. The provider's view for the potential severity of CHB can be assessed through surveys. These surveys were conducted in current studies as listed in the table of evidence (TOE; Appendix A). Information can be provided by various modalities on the potential dire consequences of improper management of CHB. Multifaceted approaches and interventions to enhance provider perceived severity may consist of graphic photos, sharing case studies, and providing statistics for the potential dire consequences of poorly managed disease (Rosenstock, Strecher, & Becker, 1988).

Perceived susceptibility. By increasing the provider's awareness of a patient's vulnerability to the disease process, there is greater perception for disease susceptibility. Chronic carriers of hepatitis B are susceptible to developing HCC. Educational seminars and webinars have increased awareness for the increasing morbidity of CHB with concurrent existing liver conditions (Marcellin, 2009). Baseline provider knowledge of CHB can be assessed through surveys to evaluate factors that shape a provider's perception for susceptibility to HCC.

Perceived benefits. An assessment of the provider's beliefs about treatment compliance is essential. The results of the studies in the literature review specifically addressed provider attitudes and beliefs in the necessity of CHB treatment. The possible interventions that can be developed to change perceived benefits include holding an online discussion and encouraging the provider to speak up on doubts on the treatment regimen of CHB. A model for encouraging action can be presented (Rosenstock et al., 1988).

Perceived barriers. Identifying a provider's personal barriers to complying with treatment guidelines can reveal solutions for improving adherence. Constructing the TOE can help to identify the most common reasons behind treatment nonadherence. Personal interviews can be used to review individual provider barriers to adhering to guidelines. Perceived barriers are minimized by providing support and developing appropriate solutions (Rosenstock et al., 1988).

Self-efficacy. Assessing provider confidence in properly adhering to the guidelines is plausible through surveys. A comprehensive search in reputable databases reviewed multiple retrospective studies with surveys that evaluated provider confidence. Further provider training can be available through webinars and conferences. Positive reinforcement and provider reimbursement through meaningful use are methods to encourage compliance (Anumula & Sanelli, 2012).

Modifying factors. Factors are elements that may have an impact on the other constructs of the HBM. These are factors that alter the course of action by the provider and influence the other constructs of the HBM (Rosenstock et al., 1988). These are nonmodifiable provider-specific features that are innate or inherent in nature. Examples

of these factors are provider demographics, culture, language, religion, personal beliefs, and existing practice factors. The concept appears self-contradictory since they modify other constructs but are fixed provider factors not amendable to change.

Modified HBM. Figure 1 depicts the modified HBM. The constructs are defined as follows: self-efficacy (provider knowledge), perceived barriers (patient culture, language, reluctance, and beliefs), perceived susceptibility (factors associated with HCC screening), perceived benefits (confidence in guidelines), and modifying factors (demographics, attitudes, and sociopsychological factors).

PRISMA Statement

The PRISMA flow diagram illustrates the study selection process. The flow diagram is a segment of the PRISMA statement that aided the selection process of the studies. The PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 2) outlines a step-by-step approach to guide the selection of research studies. The steps of the four-phase flow diagram include: identification, screening, eligibility verification, and study inclusion.

A group of multidisciplinary researchers consisting of epidemiologists and clinicians developed the PRISMA statement to standardize and improve the reporting of systematic reviews. The PRISMA statement was recently updated to the PRISMA-P 2015 initiative. The sections of the PRISMA statement include abstract, background, problem statement, purpose statement, methods, results, and discussion sections. The PRISMA statement originated from the quality of reporting of meta-analyses model, which was modified to be more applicable to systematic reviews. In over 127 health science systematic reviews and in 146 sampled medical journals comprised of systematic reviews, 27% referenced the use of the PRISMA statement (Tao et al., 2011).

Figure 1. Modified HBM.

Figure 2. PRISMA 2009 flow diagram. Adapted from “PRISMA Flow Diagram,” by PRISMA, 2015, retrieved from <http://prisma-statement.org/>.

Aims and Objectives

Multiple mixed and retrospective studies have been conducted on adherence to the CHB treatment guidelines. Until now, no systematic review has been conducted to gather all available data and analysis to summarize evidence on how to tackle the issue of lack of adherence. The aim of this project was to comprehensively review and incorporate all available studies in the literature to evaluate provider adherence to CHB treatment guidelines. A plausible solution was proposed on the basis of the literature review and the HBM as the theoretical framework. Therefore, the specific aims of this study were:

- Perform a thorough literature review on CHB treatment adherence targeted at Asian Americans
- Analyze data and findings from each study and summarize common themes
- Measure quantitatively the major themes and concepts to provider nonadherence
- Incorporate the HBM as the structural format to organize findings
- Develop plausible solutions that directly addresses the rationale for provider nonadherence.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview

There is a clear discrepancy between the number of people in the United States who are infected with hepatitis B and the number who receive treatment (Juday et al., 2010). The reasons behind this discrepancy remain largely unexplored. There is a significant disparity in the rates of CHB infection between Asian Americans and Caucasians. In the United States, Asian Americans and Pacific Islanders comprise over half of the cases of CHB. Foreign-born Asian Americans are 19.4 times more likely than those born in the United States to develop CHB (Lin, Chang, & So, 2007). A quarter of hepatitis B chronic carriers die of the disease complications, including HCC. CHB is the leading cause of primary HCC worldwide (El-Serag & Mason, 2000). Untreated CHB patients can potentially develop serious sequelae consisting of cirrhosis, decompensation, and HCC (Lin et al., 2007; Sorrell et al., 2009). Approximately 2,000 and 4,000 deaths each year in the United States are attributed to CHB infections, costing over \$1 billion annually on liver-related hospitalizations (Sorrell et al., 2009).

Despite the prevalence of CHB in the United States, many providers are unclear or unaware of the guidelines. Mitchell, Colvin, and Beasley (2010) reported from the Institute of Medicine expert review committee that both public and healthcare providers are poorly aware and uninformed on the topic of CHB.

There is a lack of adherence to guideline recommendations, suggesting that there is a potential for delaying the initiation of CHB treatment. This places patients at risk for disease progression and burden on the healthcare system (Juday et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2012). Cohen et al. (2011) estimated 25%-50% of CHB patients are treatment eligible

per AASLD and U.S. Panel guidelines, but only approximately 25% of those patients are receiving antiviral therapy. Two studies concluded that the failure for proper disease monitoring delays appropriate antiviral therapy, contributing to increased rates of complications consisting of cirrhosis, liver failure, and HCC (Juday et al., 2011; McMahon, 2005).

In another study conducted by Burman et al. (2014), the authors evaluated adherence to AASLD guidelines on hepatitis B disease monitoring. The researchers discovered that there was fallout on the provider's part to screen for HCC. As part of the AASLD guidelines, screening for HCC with imaging and alpha-fetoprotein are required. Burman et al. found that adherence to AASLD guidelines for hepatitis B management was associated with provider familiarity with guidelines and patient factors. However, only provider and practice factors were associated with the proper surveillance for HCC. This suggests that providers are a modifiable factor in improving disease management and outcomes.

In addition, Wu et al. (2014) confirmed to an even greater degree there is markedly poor adherence by providers to AASLD guidelines. They pinpointed precisely that there was a lack of appropriate laboratory monitoring, HCC surveillance, liver biopsy, and coinfection testing (Wu et al., 2014). Furthermore, Sarkar et al. (2014) confirmed from their study that HCC surveillance and laboratory monitoring of CHB were suboptimal. These findings affirm that there is a serious gap between translating guidelines into practice by providers. Sarkar et al. acknowledged that proper laboratory monitoring and HCC surveillance are essential to improving outcomes in CHB patients.

In contrast to Sarkar et al. (2014), Zhang et al. (2012) found that most patients who were eligible to receive treatment were properly initiated on treatment. The authors acknowledged this number was likely underestimating the number of patients who were treatment eligible.

Few studies have evaluated provider familiarity with disease management and current guidelines. For example, two studies found that there is a large variability of knowledge in a primary care setting from providers on the topic of CHB screening and disease management guidelines (Khalili et al., 2011; Upadhyaya et al., 2010). It remains largely unexplored to what degree of fallout to the guidelines is contributed from lack of familiarity by providers.

The multiple guidelines in practice further complicate the already complex recommendations (Zhang et al., 2012). Studies like Zhang et al. (2012), Khalili et al., (2011), and the Institute of Medicine recommend further educating providers about clinical guidelines but do not specify what approach would achieve greater adherence to the guidelines and better clinical outcomes. Furthermore, there are few studies that validate that the CHB guideline complexity is a major issue behind provider nonadherence.

Zhang et al. (2012) discovered a clear disparity in the rates of treatment between patients treated under U.S. Panel guidelines versus AASLD guidelines. By U.S. Panel guidelines, 72% of patients in their study qualified for treatment, but 29% were treatment eligible when applying AASLD guidelines. These variations in treatment rates are likely due to the lack of standardized alanine transaminase (ALT) reference ranges between the

two guidelines (Zhang et al., 2012). This leads to the question to whether provider adherence has been inaccurately assessed.

The construct of perceived severity from the HBM addresses the concept that the severity of a disease may dictate a provider's attitude for starting treatment. Zhang et al. (2012) found that treatment-eligible patients based on the U.S. Panel guidelines were likely older and already cirrhotic. The authors noted that two patients were not started treatment due to a change in providers (Zhang et al., 2012). One patient had delayed follow-up and another patient elected to wait on treatment. Delayed follow-up and failure to start treatment were fallouts on the provider's part in managing CHB. Khalili et al. (2011) showed that "provider attitudes and perceived barriers" (p. 1517) were independent predictors to HCC surveillance practices. These findings complement a study by T. T. Nguyen, Gildengorin, Truong, and McPhee (2007), which found that several notable provider factors were strongly correlated with adherence to screening. Adherence to practices were chiefly influenced by the enactment of quality control measures and the fear of malpractice.

Provider attitudes and faith in the guidelines must be evaluated as potential reasons behind nonadherence. A retrospective analysis conducted by Tong, Hsu, et al. (2011) called into question the validity of current CHB treatment guidelines. Tong, Hsu, et al. (2011) found that 30%-53% of patients with CHB who died of HCC or complicated liver disease were not treatment eligible based on current guidelines. T. T. Nguyen et al. (2007) found that both patient and provider elements influence adherence to guidelines. However, providers were especially influential on whether guidelines were followed.

Many studies have shown that recommendations made by medical providers led to increasing patient adherence to guidelines (T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007).

The majority of the current studies on CHB indirectly evaluated potential predictors of proper laboratory monitoring and treatment. Patient and provider factors that were associated with guideline adherence were analyzed through surveys, secondary outcome measures, and post hoc analysis from retrospective studies (Juday et al., 2011; L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Ku et al., 2013; Mukhtar et al., 2014). Predictors to adherence consisted of patient demographics, provider location of practice, and provider knowledge and familiarity of existing guidelines.

More research is needed to understand provider behaviors and attitudes when developing a theoretical model that would optimize management (Khalili et al., 2011; Ku et al., 2013; T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007). A theoretical approach can pave a way for creating a framework that alleviates provider nonadherence. It is plausible to develop targeted interventions based on the constructs of a framework. Provider-targeted interventions should aim to enhance knowledge for the pedantic dogma of the complex guidelines (Cabana et al., 1999; Khalili et al., 2011). Cabana et al. (1999) successfully utilized a behavior theoretical model to organize provider barriers into categories before generating a practice guideline. The HBM is a reliable theoretical model for predicting adherence (Yue, Li, & Weilin, 2015). Targeted interventional strategies may be effectively developed once provider factors are identified and organized for evaluation by the HBM. Effective targeted interventional strategies consist of a multifaceted approach with “interactive education, reminder and support systems, guideline revision” (p. 1), and feedback (Cabana et al., 1999; Prior, Guerin, & Grimmer-Somers, 2008).

Summary of Findings

Multiple studies have ascertained the need to improve adherence to CHB management guidelines (Zhang et al., 2012). No study directly addresses the rationale behind provider failure to adhere to the guidelines (Khalili et al., 2011). To date, there is no systematic review that analyzed factors that would compromise adherence to the guidelines. Furthermore, there is a paucity of studies that evaluate provider attitudes and behaviors to the management of CHB. The literature emphasizes that education has an essential role in improving provider treatment (Khalili et al., 2011; Ku et al., 2013). However, there is still a need for the development of solutions and provider-targeted interventions to facilitate adherence. Further research is necessary to evaluate the rationale for lack of adherence by providers. In addition, there is a clear lack of evidence-based recommendations that would enhance provider adherence and patient outcomes.

METHODS

Two theoretical frameworks were incorporated in this project to review and synthesize evidence. The PRISMA model and the HBM provided a structured approach for this project. A thorough literature search with specified criteria was conducted for the study selection. The PRISMA flow diagram depicts the study selection process. A TOE was constructed to organize the research studies. The PRISMA checklist provided a structured approach for the data collection, data extraction, analysis, and the synthesis and development of a guideline. The Johns Hopkins nursing evidence-based practice appraisal tool (Appendix B) was utilized to appraise the studies in this systematic review.

Search Strategy

A comprehensive search was conducted using major databases from the California State University, Fullerton, library via the following search engines: Cochrane Library, CINAHL (the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature), Medline, and PubMed. The following websites provided supplementary resources: National Guideline Clearinghouse, Google Scholar, AASLD, EASL, APASL, and the CDC. CHB management guidelines were published between 2002 and 2006 (Jung et al., 2010). Therefore, a search was conducted for literature published from the period of January 2006 to January 2016. The search consisted of the following keywords: *hepatitis B, Asian Americans, treatment, compliance, adherence, provider, and barriers*. Duplicate articles were excluded. Due to a paucity of candidate articles, a secondary search was conducted using the keywords from the guidelines: *vaccinations, HCC, laboratory monitoring, and co-infection testing*. A manual search was conducted from the reference lists of relevant articles.

Eligibility Criteria

A search was conducted for the management and/or treatment of CHB. Research articles were restricted to English-only language and human subjects. Studies that were conducted outside the United States or did not pertain to Asian American populations were excluded. Studies that did not examine or address nonadherence were also excluded. Titles and abstracts were screened with the pre-established search criteria for relevance and eligibility. Research studies that were eligible and rendered relevant at face value were further assessed.

Study Selection

The PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 3) depicts the study selection process. The flow diagram details a stepwise process with the rationale for study selection and eligibility. The initial search revealed 872 candidate articles with respect to predictors, factors, and barriers regarding adherence to CHB guidelines. A total of 836 articles were excluded after filtering the titles and abstracts for relevance. There were 36 candidate articles that met the initial screening criteria. The exclusion of the subsequent articles is depicted via the flow diagram (Figure 3). From the 36 candidate articles, three were excluded due to foreign study setting and non-English language. An additional 15 articles were excluded because they evaluated screening for CHB. The focus of this project was to investigate management of CHB and not simply disease screening. Moreover, these articles did not explore barriers to adherence or possible rationales for nonadherence. Three reviews were excluded because they were periodicals and reports from journals and not research-based systematic reviews. Seven additional articles were

Figure 3. Flow diagram for selection of articles. Adapted from “PRISMA Flow Diagram,” by PRISMA, 2015, retrieved from <http://prisma-statement.org/>.

excluded because they evaluated tools utilized in the management of CHB or did not evaluate the rationale to nonadherence.

The final 14 articles, which were included in the final literature review, employed surveys to evaluate providers' attitudes and knowledge and retrospective chart reviews of patient data. Retrospective descriptive analysis of databases, medical records, or case studies were methods employed by six studies. Six studies utilized self-reported measures to evaluate provider adherence to CHB treatment. A mixed-methods approach of retrospective chart review and provider surveys was reported in two studies.

All included studies evaluated adherence primarily with respect to four areas: (a) timely routine laboratory checks, (b) treatment initiation when indicated, (c) liver biopsy, and (d) HCC screening. Six studies evaluated adherence to routine laboratory monitoring and treatment initiation. Six studies evaluated adherence to routine laboratory monitoring, treatment initiation, and HCC screening. Two studies exclusively evaluated HCC screening as part of CHB management guidelines.

Data Extraction

One investigator (G. L.) independently extracted barriers to adherence. Two other investigators (A. T. and P. L.) reviewed and revised the findings. Studies were selected and reviewed under the PRISMA-P checklist. Each study was objectively evaluated for its methodological quality. Data were extracted, analyzed, and presented in a descriptive manner.

A TOE comprising of all eligible and potential studies was constructed after initial screening for candidate articles. Information extracted from the candidate articles was organized descriptively. The TOE shows each study's bias, inclusion and exclusion

criteria, study findings, relevance to the clinical question, study design, and methods. An appraisal of the quality of the articles was conducted.

One investigator then abstracted information via a thematic analysis of common barriers or factors for nonadherence (Table 1; Table C1 in Appendix C). A composite of the common themes and barriers was organized in accordance to the six constructs of the HBM. Two other investigators validated the organizational and barrier abstraction process. Recommendations were made based on the findings and themes from these methods.

Proposal Project

This project aimed to culminate all existing knowledge on lack of adherence to CHB guidelines. Recommendations via a framework were proposed after evaluating the studies in accordance to the constructs of the HBM.

Table 1

Composite Summary of Findings

Type	Number of factors/barriers	Factors/Barrier/Theme
Provider barriers	9 total	belief in disease severity, HCC risk (susceptibility), provider age, experience, observation, fear of complications, familiarity, knowledge, unclear guidelines
Patient barriers	22 total	race, age, sex, refusal, asymptomatic, lab stability, financial, coinfectd, previous liver biopsy, cultural, resources, ALT, HBeAg (hepatitis B e-antigen), albumin, viral load, lifespan, knowledge, loss at follow-up, resistance, longer duration of disease, frequency of visits, fear of complications, location
Practice factors	2 total	missed orders, unclear ownership
Perceived barriers	11 total 10 patient specific 1 guideline specific	resources, unclear guidelines, culture, language, fear of complications, loss at follow-up, further observation, pregnancy, no longer treatment eligible, refusal, other
All barriers	6 themes 35 total barriers	themes: self-efficacy, perceived barriers, perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, modifying factors, perceived benefits knowledge (14 studies) unclear guidelines (3 studies) lack of familiarity (1 study) lack of awareness (3 studies) provider experience (1 study) lack of confidence in guidelines (1 study)

RESULTS

Search Yield

The search yielded 14 final articles that qualified for this systematic review. Six studies were retrospective descriptive analyses of electronic charts or database reviews. Six studies employed self-reported measures. Two studies employed mixed methods of chart reviews and self-reported measures. From the 14 studies, a cumulative 36,397 patient charts were reviewed. A cumulative 1,382 providers were evaluated. The studies were primarily conducted in a community setting. Only two studies were conducted at a multicenter with a nationally representative sample. Ten of the 14 studies were conducted in Northern California, predominantly in San Francisco. Two studies were conducted in New York or New Jersey.

Themes and Barriers

There were 35 barriers to provider adherence (Table C2 in Appendix C). The thematic analysis yielded six common HBM-based themes. The barriers were classified under self-efficacy (lack of knowledge, unfamiliarity, or unawareness), perceived barriers (patient culture, language, reluctance, or beliefs), perceived severity (factors associated with routine labs and treatment), perceived susceptibility (factors associated with HCC screening), perceived benefits (confidence in the guidelines), and modifying factors (demographics, attitudes, sociopsychological factors). There were 22 patient-associated barriers to adherence. There were two practice-associated factors (missed orders and unclear patient ownership). There were eight provider-associated barriers to adherence. Two of the provider-associated barriers were perceived severity and perceived susceptibility, which are constructs from the HBM.

Lack of Self-Efficacy

Lack of awareness, familiarity, and general knowledge and unclear guidelines were the most prevalent barriers in all 14 studies. Survey respondents stated unclear guidelines, unawareness, difficult to interpret, and lack of knowledge. One study found that providers were generally knowledgeable about CHB, but 43% were unfamiliar with the guidelines (Burman et al., 2014). Primary care providers were significantly less confident and less likely to adhere to the guidelines compared to gastroenterologists, hepatologists, and infectious disease specialists (Khalili et al., 2011). Patients managed by gastroenterologists were twice as likely to have timely laboratory checks. One study identified that female providers were significantly more welcoming for further education regarding the guidelines (Ferrante, Winston, Chen, & de la Torre, 2008).

Several studies suggested that the lack of standardization with ALT reference ranges was a barrier (Skupsky & Hu, 2014; Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2012). Recommended ALT ranges for treatment eligibility differed between guidelines. The U.S. Panel had more stringent ALT reference ranges (Zhang et al., 2012). Two studies identified that failure to screen for HCC was a malpractice risk. Eight studies found that failure to screen for HCC was a common area of nonadherence, particularly among primary care physicians and infectious disease specialists (Hearn et al., 2015). Providers with a higher knowledge base were more likely to screen for HCC due to a fear of malpractice. Fear of malpractice was not a barrier but rather an incentive to adherence (Khalili et al., 2011). The two practice factors associated with nonadherence were missed orders due to staff errors and unclear ownership (Wu et al., 2014).

Perceived Barriers

There were 22 patient-associated barriers to provider adherence (Table C2 in Appendix C). Six studies specifically evaluated patient-specific barriers (Jung et al., 2010). The perceived barriers were a composite of practice-, provider-, and patient-related factors (Burman et al., 2014; Ferrante et al., 2008; Jung et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2014). The most frequently stated barriers were delayed for further observation, unclear guidelines, patient reluctance, cultural beliefs, disease stability, and limited resources (Burman et al., 2014; L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Upadhyaya et al., 2010). Other patient barriers included fear of the expenses for treatment, fear of medication or biopsy complications, and reluctance for long-term treatment (Khalili et al., 2011; Upadhyaya et al., 2010; Wu et al., 2014). Patient resistance was the greatest barrier in one study (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). One study found a positive association between greater provider age and experience with adherence and knowledge. However, only providers who had more than 20 years of experience were significantly less likely to adhere to the guidelines and had lower knowledge scores (Ferrante et al., 2008).

Modifying Factors

There were four studies that identified five modifying factors that influenced provider decisions for disease management. Providers who were older age, were male, or had greater experience were less likely to adhere to HCC screening guidelines (Burman et al., 2014; Ferrante et al., 2008). Provider attitudes and faith in the guidelines were associated with adherence (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). The evidence was conflicting regarding provider-patient culture or race with adherence (Khalili et al., 2011; Upadhyaya et al., 2010).

Perceived Susceptibility

There were eight studies that evaluated lack of adherence to HCC screening. Patient demographics and labs were predictors to adherence. Two studies found that providers ordered HCC screening by at least one testing modality when there was a presence of specific patient characteristics (older age, male sex, high ALTs, high viral load, or symptomatic clinical presentation; Khalili et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2014). Patients with these characteristics and abnormal physical findings were perceived by providers as having a greater risk for developing HCC (Khalili et al., 2011). These factors and greater provider knowledgeability were associated with higher rates for HCC screening.

Perceived Severity

There were 10 studies that identified 22 patient-associated factors (Table C2 in Appendix C) to nonadherence. Demographics and laboratory findings (Table C2 in Appendix C) were associated with perceived severity and susceptibility. Specifically, patient age and race were predictors of adherence. Being Asian, older than 40 years of age, and male sex were predictors for timely treatment. Adherence to timely laboratory monitoring, liver biopsy, and treatment initiation was associated with age older than 40 years, male sex, and patient having other concomitant liver diseases (Khalili et al., 2011). Patients with clinically advanced or severe liver disease had a greater likelihood to be referred to a specialist (Ferrante et al., 2008; Khalili et al., 2011).

Perceived Benefits

There was only one study that evaluated provider attitudes and confidence in the guidelines (T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007). Initially, several candidate articles were found to evaluate provider agreement and belief in the guidelines. However, these studies did not

meet the final eligibility criteria for this review. Two studies were found to evaluate providers' attitudes and faith in the CHB screening guidelines and not the management of the disease (Khalili et al., 2011; T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007). Providers who believed that screening for HCC reduced mortality were more likely to adhere to the guidelines. Two other studies validated that more knowledgeable providers were also more cognizant of the guidelines (Burman et al., 2014; Ferrante et al., 2008). Lack of HCC screening was perceived as a risk for litigation. Protection from litigation was an incentive and not a barrier for HCC screening.

The following is a framework that was constructed to encourage best practices and improve adherence among healthcare providers. The CHB adherence framework for Asians (CAFFA) was synthesized from the culminating evidence on barriers to managing the disease (see Figure 4). This model focuses on the behavioral and psychological aspects from the provider standpoint. Interventions target provider-specific modifiable factors (self-efficacy and perceived barriers). Several suggested additions to the recent algorithms were made to elucidate the guidelines. These suggestions conflate current evidence from various studies to simplify the guidelines by: (a) standardizing ALT reference ranges, (b) clarifying mandatory lab orders, (c) highlighting HCC screening measures, and (d) clarifying indications for liver biopsy and liver assessment. The CAFFA also defines the gray zone to treatment (i.e., patients who equivocally benefit from starting medications). Patients in the gray zone for starting treatment have low viral count but contain risk factors for active disease not detected by seromarkers (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). These patients are HBeAg negative, are suspicious carriers of the mutant variant, or have an indeterminate disease status. The CAFFA

Figure 4. CAFFA.

addresses lack of self-efficacy with unclear ownership. Unclear ownership occurs in settings where it is unclear whether the primary care provider or specialist is actively managing the disease at follow-up. Modifying factors are innate or inherent provider features that modify the other five constructs but are per se not amendable to change. Liver assessment can be performed by liver biopsy, approved noninvasive measures (serum markers or imaging), or risk impact score. The HCC screening recommendations were based on the Asian-specific review by (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011).

The Asian American algorithm (AAA) emphasizes the importance for providers to reconcile orders in order to prevent missed orders (see Figure 5). The AAA is an adapted algorithm based on the recommendations from Han and Tran (2015) and Tong, Pan, et al. (2011). Providers have the due diligence to follow up after specialist referral and consolidate recommendations. The AAA defines the upper limit of normal in serum liver enzymes. Similar to the CAFFA framework, a liver assessment can be performed via a risk impact score, serum markers, imaging, or liver biopsy. Patients who are deemed to be in high-risk groups for complications and disease progression are those with fluctuating or persistently elevated ALTs, high viral load, cirrhosis, mutant strain of CHB, low serum platelets, and low serum albumin and are more than 40 years of age, are HBeAg negative, or have family history of HCC.

Figure 5. AAA.

DISCUSSION

Barriers to Provider Adherence

Lack of Self-Efficacy

Lack of knowledge, unfamiliarity, and unclear guidelines are barriers for proper disease management and treatment. In one study, provider knowledge scores for CHB were as high as 79% (Burman et al., 2014). However, there was a lack of awareness for the guidelines in 43% of respondents (Ferrante et al., 2008). Up to 62% of primary care providers are unfamiliar with the guidelines (Dusheiko, 2013). Casual awareness is inadequate for translation into clinical practice (Cabana et al., 1999). Interpretation of the multiple and complex guidelines is time consuming and impractical for providers in a busy practice (Burman et al., 2014; Mitchell et al., 2010). Further education is a recurring proposed solution to improve adherence. However, simplification of current CPGs is most important given the overwhelming number of guidelines in clinical practice. Han and Tran (2015) have simplified current guidelines by compiling the recommendations of various societies into a simple algorithm.

Two practice factors interfered with the proper management of the disease. Missed orders were more frequent among busy practices. Providers had requested orders, but they were not carried out by the practice for unknown reasons (Wu et al., 2014). Unclear ownership of the provider responsible for managing the disease was the second practice-associated factor to nonadherence. In some practices, it was unclear which provider was responsible for the continued management of CHB once the primary care provider referred the patient to a specialist (infectious disease, gastroenterology, and hepatology; Wu et al., 2014).

Provider orders need to be reconciled at each patient visit. Implementing electronic medical record (EMR) incorporated notifications and reminders can potentially ameliorate the frequency of missed orders (Wu et al., 2014). Primary care providers have a due diligence to follow up on their respective specialists to resolve the issue of unclear ownership.

Perceived Barriers

Perceived barriers impede providers from adhering to guidelines. These barriers may be patient-, provider-, or practice-specific factors that pose difficulties to the provider. These barriers delay treatment initiation, HCC screening, and/or timely laboratory checks. Patient knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs are commonly perceived barriers against proper disease management and treatment. It was unclear why one study found a statistically significant association between more than 20 years of experience of provider and nonadherence and lower knowledge scores (Ferrante et al., 2008). Other patient barriers included fear of expenses for treatment, fear of medication or biopsy complications, and reluctance for indefinite treatment (Cohen et al., 2011). Many Asian American patients believe that disease management is necessary only when symptoms present (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). Patient resistance was identified as the greatest barrier in one study (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). These findings reinforce the importance of educating patients and dispelling any myths regarding treatment. Patients need to be aware that improperly managed CHB can potentially progress despite the often asymptomatic presentation (Chen et al., 2006).

Culture and language. Asian populations are fearful, distrustful, and unfamiliar with Western medicine (Tran, 2009). These factors delay starting treatment and regular

disease monitoring. It is important to reassure patients that long-term data for management and treatment regimens are robust. It is important to educate patients that severe adverse effects are rare and that halting the progression of the disease is a priority (Tran, 2009).

Cultural sensitivity, language congruency, and proper rapport are factors that may play a role in patient adherence. A language barrier and impaired communication presumably impede the proper management in Asian Americans. Studies have validated culture, language, and problems understanding the healthcare system as the main patient barriers to adherence (Hwang, Roundtree, Engebretson, & Suarez-Almazor, 2010; Wiegand, van Bommel, & Berg, 2010). Community access programs have been proposed to alleviate these barriers (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). One recent study found that there were no significant differences in HBV screening rates between Asian-speaking providers and non-Asian-speaking providers (Khalili et al., 2011). This may suggest that the burden is on the provider and that a lack of provider awareness is a predominant factor to nonadherence. Incongruous culture or language between patients and providers is not a barrier according to the Khalili et al. (2011) study. Nevertheless, providers have a due diligence to properly communicate in a culturally sensitive manner to their patients to foster trust and understanding.

Patient reluctance. There is poor patient compliance to CHB management due to the asymptomatic nature of the disease and lack of patient understanding regarding the disease course (Tran & Ocampo, 2012). The long-term benefits are not appreciated, while the inconvenience of frequent office visits and lab draws are not appealing to patients. These reasons may explain nonadherence and patient loss at follow-up (Tran &

Ocampo, 2012). A study by Zhang et al. (2012) validated these findings as the primary reasons for delaying treating. Patients need education regarding the expected course of CHB and the risks of poorly managed disease.

Further observation was the most commonly stated rationale for failing to treat (Ku et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2012). Patients fear the potential adverse drug reactions and the commitment to chronic therapy (L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Upadhyaya et al., 2010). Furthermore, nearly 20% of Asians distrust Western medicine and prefer alternative medicine (Tran, 2009). Patients need to be educated that several studies have validated that long-term therapy is safe and has few adverse effects (Gordon et al., 2014; Liaw et al., 2004). Despite potential cultural barriers, patients were found to adhere to treatment regimens the majority of the time once started by the provider (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). This may suggest that the burden of proper disease management is on the provider.

Perceived Severity

Patients who were perceived to have severe disease (advanced disease, rapid progression, or resistant to treatment) were likely to be referred to a specialist or monitored closely (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). Providers routinely monitored labs and started treatment in the setting of serious disease (Juday et al., 2011). Treatment is indicated for individuals who are at high risk for liver complications. These individuals have advanced liver disease or manifest with persistently high viral loads or ALTs (Han & Tran, 2015). Primary care physicians have the lowest rates for using recommended treatments (Sarkar et al., 2014). The first-line preferred agents are pegylated interferon-alpha, entecavir, or tenofovir (EASL, 2012; Liaw et al., 2008; Lok & McMahon, 2009). Periodic routine interval checks for viral load, ALT, and serologic responses are indicated

in treatment (Han & Tran, 2015). Patients who are not treatment eligible will require frequent laboratory monitoring for disease progression.

Perceived Susceptibility

Providers perceived several patient factors (age, sex, viral load, ALT) as a greater risk for developing HCC. Patients considered at a high risk for HCC require ultrasound every 6 months (Han & Tran, 2015). Although several risk calculators have been disseminated for use, the risk impact score incorporates several biochemical and demographic features (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). Use of risk calculators is appropriate to evaluate cases with equivocal risks for HCC.

Wu et al. (2014) acknowledged a study that showed an enhancement in provider adherence to esophageal variceal management once EMR order sets were incorporated into practice (Mayorga & Rockey, 2013). Another study confirmed that the incorporation of EMR reminders for hepatitis A and B improved provider rates for ordering vaccinations (Waldorf, Gill, & Crosby, 2014). The use of decision support tools, reminders, and risk assessments that are built into the EMR may improve adherence. The implementation of these tools in disease management may improve provider adherence.

Perceived Benefits

A provider's confidence in the guidelines may be a factor with adherence. Despite conflicting findings, providers agreed that adhering to the guidelines improved patient outcomes (Cabana et al., 1999; T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007). In addition, providers were four times more likely to adhere to the guidelines if the provisions were a quality of care measure (T. T. Nguyen et al., 2007). In one study, 83% of providers acknowledged that CHB was an extremely serious disease (Upadhyaya et al., 2010). Mandating quality

of care measures for CHB management in specialty settings is a strategy to increase adherence.

Modifying Factors

Modifying factors are a provider's personality, attitude, and sociopsychological and demographic variables that may manipulate a provider's perceptions and beliefs. These factors can shape the provider's perception of the benefits, barriers, and self-efficacy to adherence (Rosenstock et al., 1988). These innate and inherent factors are resistant to change. Further education is an avenue that may shape a provider's attitude regarding the perception of the disease. Providers who were older in age and had greater experience were less likely to adhere to the guidelines for unclear reasons (Burman et al., 2014). Further investigation regarding the etiology of lack of adherence in this group is needed.

Additional Recommendations

Difficult and unclear guidelines were commonly reported barriers by providers (Burman et al., 2014; Khalili et al., 2011; Mukhtar et al., 2014). Lack of understanding and nonadherence were more common among primary care providers (L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Ku et al., 2013). Near the completion of this project, a periodical was published to compile the guidelines from various societies into a simplified algorithm to assist primary care providers with the management of CHB (Han & Tran, 2015). Another set of Asian-specific recommendations based on a recent literature review from a panel of Asian American hepatitis B experts was published in 2011 (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). The following are suggestions that should be considered in conjunction with the recently published recommendations by Tong, Pan, et al. (2011) and Han and Tran (2015).

Areas of Nonadherence

There are four key areas to CHB management that providers need to make note of: (a) timely interval lab testing, (b) starting treatment when indicated, (c) liver biopsy to determine indication for treatment, and (d) HCC screening.

Laboratory tests. After the initial workup, proper laboratory monitoring should consist of ALT, viral load, and HBeAg every 3-6 months (Kumar et al., 2008; Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). Additional individualized studies may be needed for specific subgroups (Kumar et al., 2008; Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011).

Treatment rates differ significantly depending on what CPGs were employed in practice—U.S. Panel guidelines and AASLD guidelines (L. H. Kim et al., 2014). Further observation was the most commonly stated rationale for delaying treatment. Researchers of several studies surmised that providers were adopting a conservative approach, hesitant to start indefinite treatment, or unclear of the guidelines (L. H. Kim et al., 2014; Wu et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2012). Lack of standardization of ALT treatment ranges was a factor for delaying treatment. There was an association with viral load and the risk for HCC in patients who were not treatment eligible (Tong, Hsien, Hsu, Sun, & Blatt, 2008). Patients with ALT levels within the upper limit of normal were still at risk for developing complications (Yuen et al., 2005). Providers should consider employing the more stringent reference laboratory ranges. The most current literature suggests that the upper limit of normal for ALT is 30 IU/mL in men and 19 IU/mL in women (Han & Tran, 2015; Yuen & Lai, 2011).

A retrospective study found that 19%-20% of patients who died of liver complications and 23%-53% of patients who eventually developed HCC were not

candidates for treatment per current CPGs (Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011). The inclusion of albumin and platelet levels as a risk assessment would render 85%-94% of these cases as eligible for treatment. The addition of precore and basal core promotor CHB variants would further increase treatment eligibility to 98.5%-100%. CHB mutant testing and additional laboratory workup to evaluate perceivably high-risk patients for treatment may be a prudent approach to management (Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011).

Liver biopsies. A liver biopsy is indicated for evaluating equivocal CHB cases before starting treatment (EASL, 2012). Patients in the gray zone for starting treatment have low viral count but contain risk factors for active disease not detected by seromarkers (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). These patients are HBeAg negative, are suspicious carriers of the mutant variant, or have an indeterminate disease status. Older patients with longstanding disease will require biopsy. Patients with fluctuating ALTs, borderline normal ALTs, or a family history of HCC will also need biopsy (EASL, 2012; Han & Tran, 2015). Liver biopsy evaluates the degree of fibrosis, necroinflammation, coinfection, and other liver conditions (Bedossa, Dargere, & Paradis, 2003; Chen et al., 2006; Iloeje et al., 2006). Fear of complications from biopsy is a common barrier for both patient and provider. However, actual rates of complications are low (Bedossa et al., 2003). The risk impact score and noninvasive tests (serum markers, imaging elastography) are acceptable alternatives to liver biopsy (EASL, 2012; Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). Patients with overt active disease may start treatment without liver biopsy.

HCC screening. Failure to screen for HCC was a common area of nonadherence. Primary care providers and infectious disease specialists were less likely to screen for HCC. Provider unawareness and practice factors accounted for failure to screen.

Abdominal ultrasound and alpha-fetoprotein is required every 6 months to evaluate HCC in high-risk groups (Tong, Pan, et al., 2011). This is a cost-effective approach to screen for HCC (Eckman, Kaiser, & Sherman, 2011; Veldhuijzen et al., 2010). Patients considered at a high risk for developing complications or HCC are: Asian men more than 40 years old, Asian women more than 50 years old, cirrhotic patients, patients with a family history of HCC, Africans more than 20 years old, and any carrier more than 40 years old with recurring or persistently elevated ALTs and/or viral load above 2,000 IU/mL (Han & Tran, 2015; Liaw et al., 2008; Lok & McMahon, 2009).

Cost Effectiveness

Studies validate that screening, management, and early treatment is most cost effective when considering long-term outcomes. Early treatment and management is a cost-effective approach to even areas with an extremely low prevalence of disease (Han et al., 2012; Yuen & Lai, 2011). Carriers with inactive HBV still have a substantial risk of HCC and other disease complications (Chen, Iloeje, & Yang, 2007). Therefore, early treatment is economical with a low-cost nucleoside or nucleotide analogue. Early screening and management are cost-effective approaches in contrast to the exorbitant expenses of end-of-life care, palliative care, or hospitalizations (Hutton, Brandeau, & So, 2011; Spackman & Veenstra, 2008). A study by Hutton et al. (2011) proved that in the United States it is cost effective to screen, vaccinate, and treat Asian and Pacific Islanders. This work was the impetus that changed CHB policy and promoted guideline awareness. Policymakers and insurance companies need to recognize that early and proper treatment is necessary and cost effective.

Fear of Overtreatment

The potential for overtreatment is presumably low in Asian Americans. This population carries CHB mutant variants that are more likely to progress to HCC even in the setting of inactive disease, low viral loads, and normal liver function tests (Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011). Despite the widespread dissemination of numerous guidelines, 30%-53% of patients still developed liver complications and HCC (Tong, Hsu, et al., 2011). The findings of another reputable review support the notion that CHB is being undertreated in the United States (Cohen et al., 2011). Dr. Keeffe's panel of researchers delivered recommendations that emphasized individualizing treatment (Keeffe et al., 2008). Providers should not delay treatment due to fear of overtreatment or for delayed observation. CHB management should be patient centered and personalized to encourage adherence.

Refer to Specialist

Primary care providers who managed CHB more frequently were more knowledgeable and adhered more closely to the guidelines (Burman et al., 2014; Jung et al., 2010). A recent study found that providers who managed more than six cases of CHB per year were more confident, aware, and familiar with the guidelines (Ferrante et al., 2008). Up to 42% of primary care providers were unaware of the guidelines (Kallman et al., 2009). The researchers highlighted the importance of provider education and that knowledge was associated with greater adherence (Kallman et al., 2009). It may prudent for primary care providers who infrequently manage CHB to consider referring to a specialist.

Comment

Several recent reviews and periodicals were published to assist providers with the management of CHB. Most of these articles are targeted at primary care providers. A recent review by Cohen et al. (2011) validated the findings that gastroenterologists were more likely than infectious disease specialists or primary care providers to screen for HCC. The authors acknowledged there was a lack of understanding for this disparity but posited that this incongruence was due to personal provider barriers that included lack of knowledge, cultural beliefs, and fear of stigmatization (Cohen et al., 2011). Their hypotheses were not validated by descriptive analysis and were not explored in detail. Their review did not specifically discuss or evaluate psychosocial or behavioral factors for nonadherence. Tong et al. (2008) reviewed and evaluated the existing treatment recommendations in Asian Americans. The authors published specific recommendations and a simplified algorithm for CHB management. They descriptively analyzed the efficacy of current guidelines in regard to patient outcomes. As with Cohen et al., there were considerations or evaluations of provider-specific psychosocial and behavioral factors.

In hindsight, Han and Tran (2015) published their periodical to improve adherence at the end of 2015. They gleaned the evidence, consolidated guidelines from the various societies, and generated several simplified algorithms to assist primary care providers with the management of CHB. However, their algorithms were not customized to different ethnic backgrounds. The algorithms were not tailored specifically for Asian Americans. There were no considerations regarding psychosocial, behavioral, and cultural factors.

This review was the first to descriptively analyze factors and barriers to adherence. This project was the first to address psychosocial, behavioral, and cultural factors associated with provider nonadherence by providing a preliminary framework and algorithm specifically tailored to the Asian American population.

Facilitating provider adherence requires employing multifaceted approaches. This encompasses the use of didactic measures, interactive strategies, clinical decision support programs, risk assessment calculators, EMR reminders, and simplified guidelines. Effective education should encourage the development of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills (Billings & Halstead, 2012). Simply promulgating the guidelines and the use of traditional classroom methods may be inadequate to elicit change (Prior et al., 2008).

Project Appraisal and Limitations

The studies included in this review were primarily retrospective chart reviews and surveys of providers. Self-reported measures are subject to response bias that may overestimate answers on knowledge assessment and clinical outcomes. The inherent limitations of retrospective studies are the potential for missed barriers and a tendency to overexaggerate findings. The retrospective nature of this review does not directly evaluate the attitudes and behaviors of providers. In addition, this review did not explore deeper reasons that dictate a provider's behavior. There is limited evidence on the clinical utility of the HBM on adopting change. This project proposes an untested framework for the purpose of improving adherence to the guidelines. This framework has not been evaluated in clinical practice.

This review was comprised of articles appraised at a Level V evidence with an overall B quality rating based on the Johns Hopkins nursing evidence-based practice appraisal tool. The preponderance of descriptive methods yielded relatively homogeneous results among the studies and strengthened the findings of this review. Thematic abstraction and barrier evaluation by comparative analysis between studies were plausible. The weakness of this review is from the studies' descriptive methods per se. All of the articles employed descriptive analysis to self-reported measures and retrospective chart reviews. Descriptive methods reveal data, descriptions, and associations with multivariate analysis but not causal relationships. The homogeneous methodology of six studies (i.e., self-reported measures) improves the concurrent validity for this systematic review (Polit & Beck, 2012).

Conclusion

Numerous barriers were associated with poor adherence. Provider-targeted interventions are necessary to facilitate guideline adherence. The strategies proposed in the literature were educational conferences with interactive interventions, EMR-embedded clinical decision support programs, EMR reminders, patient-specific interventions, and guidelines simplification (Prior et al., 2008; Wu et al., 2014). Simply promulgating the guidelines is ineffective in changing practice habits (Jung et al., 2010; Prior et al., 2008).

This project evaluates treatment disparity from a different perspective and places the burden of disease management on the providers and their practices. The CAFFA framework provides a foundation for future models addressing nonadherence from a

behavioral and psychosocial standpoint. This framework is intended as a preliminary model that offers suggestions to improve the management of the disease.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Summary of Studies for Chronic Hepatitis B Screening and Management

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
Identify HBV disease monitoring patterns and factors a/w adherence to guidelines in primary care (Burman et al., 2014)	Prospective cross-sectional survey of PCPs Retrospective review of pt records	<i>N</i> = 148 PCPs in San Francisco primary care clinics <i>N</i> = 1,737 pt records	Provider survey of management practices, attitudes, barriers, and knowledge reported as composite scores Pt records revealed for (a) adherence to management and (b) adherence to HCC screening	45% response. 79% reported ALT and 44% reported HBV DNA ordered every 6-12 months Most providers were generally knowledgeable about HBV but 43% unfamiliar with AASLD 65% of PCPs reported not screening for HCC is a malpractice risk. 51% screening rate Asian race (OR 4.18, 95% CI 2.40-7.27) and patient age a/w HBV monitoring Perceived barriers: lack of resources (26%), guideline unawareness (25%), and unclear guidelines (25%)	Conclusions: AASLD familiarity and patient factors were a/w HBV monitoring Only provider and practice factors a/w HCC screening Provider knowledge and attitudes positively associated Provider age and perceived barriers negatively associated with HCC surveillance Need provider-targeted interventions Limitations: retrospective database review but prospective survey with 45% response rate. Self-report tends to overestimate behavior

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				Provider knowledge and attitudes positively associated and provider age and perceived barriers negatively associated with HCC surveillance	Notes: study measures all aspects of adherence including knowledge, attitudes, and barriers. First study that measures patient, provider, and practice factors
Examine the rate and factors associated with adherence to CHB tx (Chotiyaputta, Peterson, Ditah, Goodwin, & Lok, 2011)	Retrospective chart review Persistence and adherence rates and variables associated	<i>N</i> = 11,000 pts from three cohorts in pharmacy database	Persistence = continuing med acquisition for 12-month period Adherence = percentage of days of taking medications as prescribed Pt demographics and treatment status (new/existing)	4.7% newly started on tx; 95.3% already on tx Mean persistence 81 ± 3.8%; higher in existing pts (81.4% vs. 73.4%; <i>p</i> < 0.001) Mean adherence 87.8 ± 19.1%; higher in existing pts (88% vs. 84.6%; <i>p</i> = 0.001) New pts (OR = 0.68, 95% CI 0.53-0.86) and young pts (OR = 0.82, 95% CI 0.74-0.91) unlikely to adhere at > 90% rate	Conclusions: first largest study on pt adherence to long-term NA therapy Adherence and persistence to therapy high in CHB pts. Education for younger pts recommended to decrease tx resistance Limitations: retrospective noninterventional study using descriptive analysis Notes: highly recognized large study on pt adherence to treatment
Evaluate the cost effectiveness of screening CHB in populations of low prevalence of disease (Eckman, Kaiser, &	Retrospective statistical calculations Cost effectiveness	Existing data from National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys between 1988 and 1994 in	Markov state transition model to examine screening of asymptomatic pts Effectiveness =	Low-cost, high-resistance NAs were cost effective (\$29,230 per QALY) Screening costs = \$50,000 per QALY for very low-	Conclusions: screening with subsequent tx with a low-cost, high-resistance NA for CHB in populations of extremely low prevalence is cost effective Limitations: little details on

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
Sherman, 2011)		United States	QALYs	risk populations	development of Markov state transition model or calculations of sensitivity analyses to derive results. Calculations based on assumptions on existing data
Examine PCPs' knowledge and practices for CHB and screening for HCC (Ferrante, Clinton, Chen, & de la Torre, 2008)	Prospective cross-sectional mailed survey Outcomes on knowledge of risk factors, screening, counseling for chronic HBV or HCV, and screening for HCC	<i>N</i> = 217 PCPs members of New Jersey Academy of Family Physicians	Knowledge risk factor scale from 0 to 9 analyzed by descriptive analysis via SPSS	Mean knowledge score 79% for CHB. Knowledge of risk factors lowest in physicians with > 20 years of experience and highest in those in practice < 5 years 21% of PCPs unaware what to do after screen positive with HBsAg 83% interested in further education. Preferred literature by mail (53%) or pocket card (43%). One third preferred a dinner meeting (33%) or conference (30%). Gender significantly a/w interest in education (89% female vs. 73% male) Physicians managing six or	Conclusions: PCPs lack knowledge in screening and counseling for HCC Limitations: single cohort study of PCPs with pilot-tested survey validated by one hepatologist. High response rate (62%). Surveys tend to overestimate positive behavior

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				more cases/year more knowledgeable on CHB	
				25% screened for HCC. 42% and 51% referred to specialists for chronic HBV and HCV, respectively. No differences in PCP and practice characteristics	
Compare HIV provider (ID) and hepatologist (GI) adherence to AASLD guidelines (Hearn et al., 2015)	Retrospective database review with coinfecting HIV/HBV pts Cross-sectional SurveyMonkey for providers Chart review of medical record database	<i>N</i> = 144 (HIV/HBV coinfecting) and <i>N</i> = 225 (HBV monoinfected) large metropolitan academic center	Primary endpoint—IDs compared to GIs in HCC screening. Secondary endpoint—monitoring viral loads, HBeAg, and HAV immunity Survey—evaluate provider knowledge	IDs (36%) screened HCC less than GIs (81.8%) 1.8% of HIV/HBV coinfecting pts had HCC compared to 16% of monoinfected pts Older pt age a/w with lower HCC screening rates IDs screened HAV immunity but less for routine labs compared to GIs Poorly controlled HIV a/w detectable HBV DNA Survey—GIs more comfortable with CHB pts than IDs. IDs more comfortable with coinfecting pts. GIs follow	Conclusions: ID providers' poor adherence to guidelines are multifactorial; failure to order tests and pt noncompliance. AASLD guidelines do not directly address coinfection Education recommended for IDs Limitations: study limited d/t retrospective nature. Small sample, one setting. Possible incomplete charting. Possible lab tests ordered but not done Notes: compares IDs to GIs in HIV/HBV coinfecting pts. Consider referral to hepatology for monoinfected and ID for coinfecting pts

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
Subanalysis of REVEAL study. Evaluate the relationship of CHB viremia with progression to cirrhosis in untreated pts (Iloeje et al., 2006)	Longitudinal 12-year population-based prospective study HBV DNA levels in correlation with incidences of cirrhosis	<i>N</i> = 23,820 pts from Taiwan 3,584 HBsAg positive and 18,541 HBsAg negative pts as controls	Incidence of cirrhosis in untreated pts versus controls Statistical analysis of HBV DNA level with different strata of risk factors for progression to cirrhosis Cirrhosis diagnosed on ultrasound scoring system	Low HBV DNA, inactive disease, and also at risk for HCC compared to pts with HBsAg negative or undetectable viral load Positive correlation with viral load and developing cirrhosis despite ALT levels < 45 U/L, HBeAg negative, and no sonographic evidence of cirrhosis Risk of cirrhosis independent of ALT or HBeAg status Cirrhotic rates increase from 5% for viral load of < 300 copies/mL to 36% for pts with viral load of > 10 ⁶ copies/mL (<i>p</i> < .001)	Conclusions: viral load is critical to progression of CHB infection; antiviral tx mandatory to halt progression. A load of > 10 ⁴ copies/mL a/w risk of progression Limitations: supportive study for disease severity. Setting in Taiwan of one population. Ultrasound scoring system validated to an antiquated biopsy study from 1993
Evaluate provider adherence with monitoring labs per AASLD criteria in CHB not actively treated; determine	Retrospective descriptive cohort review of medical records Key variables:	<i>N</i> = 16,120 from Ingenix database containing healthcare claims in outpatient and inpatient settings	Laboratory testing: Frequency of laboratory testing for ALT and DNA levels per AASLD criteria Predictors:	Laboratory testing: 53.3% of pts were monitored at least every 12 months. DNA levels checked in 39% of pts. 35.1% of pts were checked for both	Conclusions: poor adherence to guidelines in commercially insured pts for lab testing—ALT and DNA; one third of pts received both tests annually Lab monitoring for untreated pts

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
predictors of proper laboratory monitoring and starting tx (Juday et al., 2011)	Adherence to laboratory testing per AASLD criteria Predictors for laboratory monitoring and starting antiviral tx	across United States	Multivariate logistic regression to analyze predictors of monitoring ALT and DNA levels Disease burden measured by Deyo-Charlson Comorbidity Index	ALT and DNA levels. 93.7% of pts were checked for labs at any given point in time during f/u Predictors for laboratory testing: males and located in the Northeast Predictors for starting antiviral tx: pts who had DNA level, males, and higher Deyo-Charlson Comorbidity Index scores	poor, suggesting delay in tx initiation. ALT monitored frequently than viral load (monitored for other reasons) Limitations: retrospective study via database comprising solely of commercial insurance claims. No control for variables and does not include undocumented pts or federal programs. Tool details not discussed Notes: evaluates adherence in pts not receiving tx
Determine rates of lab monitoring and treatment in low-income and immigrant CHB pts (Jung et al., 2010)	Review of medical records to measure pretx evaluation and tx when indicated Evaluated factors associated with outcomes	<i>N</i> = 1,231 pts from four gastroenterology clinics in Los Angeles County Department of Health Services	Outcomes: (a) receipt of pretx HBV evaluation and (b) receipt of tx for CHB Pt demographics and characteristics a/w tx	Asians were most common ethnic group (45%), with a mean sample age of 42 years Variables a/w with tx initiation included: male sex, African American race, HIV coinfection, previous liver bx, HBeAg status, viral count, younger age, lower albumin, longer duration of CHB, frequent GI visits, and recent provider contact. Asian race a/w not receiving tx	Conclusions: management and tx of CHB pts in a low-income and immigrant population is suboptimal Hypothesizes that providers dealing with pts with higher prevalence of infection are more aware of tx Limitations: variables not thoroughly reviewed d/t chart review. Only 56% of pt charts available, skewing results. Sample comprised largely of uninsured pts. Rationale for not

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
Update and provide clarification for current guidelines (Keeffe et al., 2008)	Design: systematic review Key variables: guidelines from	Conglomeration of studies	Tx indications HCC screening modalities and frequency	<p>Significant increased association of receiving tx when HIV positive</p> <p>Providers became more aware of tx indications when guidelines published in 2002-2006</p> <p>Most pts (84%) with CHB in a publically funded system did not receive tx</p> <p>Predictors for starting tx: HIV coinfection and frequent visits to GI clinics. Rationale was dual coverage with HIV meds. Secondly, providers of coinfectd pts were specialists and more familiar with guidelines than PCPs. Frequent visits to specialists a/w with appropriate tx</p>	<p>starting tx unknown. Barriers to patient-provider need to be further evaluated</p> <p>Notes: study reinforces referral to specialists. Results similar to Zhang et al. (2012) study</p> <p>Conclusions: treatment for CHB should be individualized</p> <p>Limitations: inherent limitations of a review including</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
	various societies		HCC risk groups	<p>have active disease at lower levels)</p> <p>Tx initiation individualized. First-line tx: entecavir, tenofovir, and peg-interferon</p> <p>If resistance, then continue and add different drug class</p> <p>HCC screening by AFP and liver US every 6 months</p> <p>HCC risk groups: Asian men > 40 years, Asian women > 50, Asians infected at birth > 30, Africans > 20, cirrhotic, family hx of HCC, or ALT > ULN or high DNA levels</p>	<p>overstatement of findings and potential bias.</p> <p>Noninterventional review of current literature</p> <p>Notes: first researchers to recommend individualizing therapy and not strictly adhering to guidelines</p>
Evaluate HCC screening practices in CHB pts in practices with large Asian American populations (Khalili et al., 2011)	Cross-sectional survey of providers regarding HCC screening practices	N = 109 respondents in clinics within San Francisco's healthcare system consisting of primary care, GI, ID, and hepatology	Provider and practice characteristics, CHB screening and management practices, HCC surveillance and modalities employed, provider knowledge	<p>72% response rate to survey. Pt population in corresponding clinics mostly uninsured or had public insurance</p> <p>Large variation in HCC screening practices and</p>	<p>Conclusions: having more Asian pts a/w higher rates of screening. No association between provider race or ability to speak an Asian language with increased screening</p> <p>Familiarity of guidelines and not pt factors a/w with adherence</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
			of CHB, and perceived barriers	<p>modalities utilized. AFP and US most frequently utilized in combination every 6-12 months (88%). 63% used US, 8% used computed tomography, and 29% used multiple imaging types. 3% used AFP alone and 5% used imaging alone</p> <p>Nearly all providers aware of HCC screening and CHB as a higher incidence in Asians. 70% believed screening reduces HCC mortality and more than half believed cost effective and failure to screen as a malpractice risk</p> <p>Perceived barriers: lack of imaging resources, unclear guidelines, lack of specialty care, and financial barriers</p> <p>Factors a/w HCC screening: CHB screening, HBV vaccination, guideline awareness, and provider younger than 40</p>	<p>Suggests provider-targeted interventions d/t lack of familiarity of guidelines</p> <p>Knowledge a/w increased screening and fear of malpractice. No association found in provider characteristics or demographics and practices or attitudes</p> <p>Limitations: self-reported survey that tend towards overestimation of screening. Practices consisted of high Asian populations</p> <p>Notes: analyzed provider-perceived barriers to HCC surveillance. Analyzed provider attitudes, knowledge, and barriers to HCC screening</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				years old. HCC screening higher among providers with Asian pts and higher knowledge scores	
Evaluate the fraction of pts eligible for tx at 6-month f/u and measure the number of pts treated at 12-month f/u by PCP, GI, and hepatology; secondary aims included determining predictors of tx and reasons for lack of tx (L. H. Kim et al., 2014)	Retrospective descriptive review of medical records Key variables: tx eligibility via U.S. Panel and AASLD criteria Tx status Predictors for starting and being eligible for tx	<i>N</i> = 1,976 from computer query for CHB. Medical record reviews and case report forms from a university liver clinic, community GI clinics, or primary care clinics	Tx eligibility: U.S. Panel criteria HBeAg positive pts with DNA > 20,000 IU/mL and ALT > 19 U/L in women or 30 U/L in men. Compensated cirrhosis with DNA > 2,000 IU/mL. Decompensated cirrhosis; tx with detectable DNA levels AASLD criteria DNA > 20,000 IU/mL and ALT levels > 2x ULN. Compensated cirrhosis with DNA levels > 2,000 IU/mL. Decompensated cirrhosis with detectable DNA levels	Eligibility: U.S. Panel criteria—fewer pts were eligible for tx in the PCP group compared to GI and hepatology group at 6-month f/u (37% vs. 54% and 53%, respectively) AASLD criteria—the PCP group also less likely eligible for tx (9% vs. 25% and 24%, respectively) Tx status: rates differed between the three groups. For U.S. Panel criteria, PCP had lowest rates (25%) and hepatology the highest rates (59%). For AASLD criteria, PCP tx rates were higher in GI and hepatology (50% vs. 68% and 50% vs. 73%) Predictors for starting and being eligible for tx: higher ALT and DNA, male, age	Conclusions: significant disparity in the proportion of pts who received tx. Pts benefit from specialty management. Providers and pts require more education especially with pts < 50 years old and female pts Seeing specialist independent predictor for tx AASLD higher threshold for tx. Gender disparity with females less likely to be started tx Limitations: retrospective design. Sample comprises of mainly Asian pts limiting generalizability. Does not explore details behind pt refusal for tx and physician delaying onset of tx. Inferential statistics with no additional details Notes: good comparison of three groups of physicians in different fields of practice

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
			<p>Tx status: any of seven FDA-approved medications for CHB</p> <p>Predictors: multivariate analysis using both hep B guidelines</p>	<p>> 50, and referral to specialty clinics were associated with meeting tx criteria; male and age > 50 were predictors for tx by 12 months</p> <p>Reasons for nontreatment: further observation and perceived normal ALT. Pt refusal ranged from 14% to 27%</p> <p>< 50% of tx-eligible pts were started tx in the PCP group</p>	
Evaluate the management of CHB with current tx criteria by PCPs and specialists; secondary aims to explain the disparity between the two groups (Ku et al., 2013)	<p>Retrospective descriptive review of medical records using case report forms at two time intervals</p> <p>Key variables: Optimal evaluation for CHB per AASLD and U.S. Panel criteria Tx status</p> <p>Explanations for</p>	<i>N</i> = 253 pts from EMRs in San Francisco Bay Area at community multispecialty centers	<p>Optimal evaluation: screened with all three laboratory parameters (ALT, e-antigen status, and DNA)</p> <p>Tx status: therapy started on interferon, adefovir, or entecavir</p> <p>Explanations: documentation in in case reports</p>	<p>Optimal evaluation: PCPs less likely to check all three labs compared to specialists (33% vs. 62%)</p> <p>ALT, e-antigen status, and DNA level checked by: PCPs (86%, 41%, and 52%, respectively) and specialists (94%, 67%, and 83%, respectively). A small fraction (20%-30%) of pts seen by PCPs or specialists did not receive tx</p>	<p>Conclusions: one third of pts seen by PCPs checked the three main labs as recommended</p> <p>PCPs more likely to prescribe older Rx agents</p> <p>Pts would benefit from a specialty visit</p> <p>All three labs are necessary in specialty setting (HBeAg, ALT, and HBV DNA), with additional tests for subgroups</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
	lack of tx			Explanations for lack of tx: delay for observation, pt refusal, plans for pregnancy, and other	<p>Limitations: small sample sizes in both groups. Population consisted of primarily Asians. Explanations for lack of treatment not discussed by authors. Need to evaluate details for pt refusal</p> <p>Notes: small sample but good comparison between PCP and specialty. Strongly suggests specialty visit for disease management</p>
Lamivudine for patients with CHB and advanced liver disease (Liaw et al., 2004)	Design: prospective double-blind randomized controlled trial Key variables: disease progression	<i>N</i> = 651 from multicenter of unlisted locations	Progression: hepatic decompensation, HCC, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, bleeding varices, and death	<p>Study terminated early due to clear difference in endpoints</p> <p>Child-Pugh score increased 3.4% in lamivudine group compared to 8.8% in placebo</p> <p>HCC in 3.9% of lamivudine group and 7.4% in placebo</p> <p>Resistance developed in 49% of patients on lamivudine</p>	<p>Conclusions: continuous treatment delays disease progression</p> <p>Limitations: low powered study. Not generalizable to other ethnic groups. Predominantly Asian population</p> <p>Notes: classic study on benefits of long-term NA for viral suppression. Results congruent with Gordon et al. (2014) study</p>
Evaluate hepatitis B screening and	Design: mixed retrospective,	<i>N</i> = 20,574 from a primary care	Screening, vaccination, and	Provider surveys, vaccination, and screening:	Conclusions: providers underutilized screening and

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
vaccination practices by reviewing pt records and conducting provider surveys (Mukhtar et al., 2014)	prospective, descriptive review of medical records; self-reported surveys Key variables: screening and vaccination status	electronic query in San Francisco <i>N</i> = 330 providers surveyed from primary care clinics in San Francisco Community Health Network	barriers: self-reported by provider on survey Survey instrument developed by study's authors with input and validation from peer physicians Screening and vaccination: identified on EMR with hep B tests and documented vaccination	one third of providers reported more than 75% screening rates in their high-risk pts. HBsAg used to screen almost all pts. 20.9% of providers reported vaccinating 75% of eligible pts Barriers cited: difficult guidelines, unawareness, and pt financial hardship Chart review vaccination and screening: 38.5% of pts had no testing. 47.4% of HBV-susceptible pts vaccinated	vaccination practices. Hep B practices are mainly influenced by provider attitudes and perceived barriers Limitations: retrospective with 45% response rate and survey-related bias. Survey instrument had insufficient testing and validation. Generalizability limited due to sample studied comprised of immigrants. Barriers identified but not explored Notes: study identified clear barriers
Evaluate physician factors a/w HCC screening (T. T. Nguyen, Gildengorin, Truong, & McPhee, 2007)	Design: cross-sectional survey to randomly selected providers (GIs, PCPs, and nephrologists) Key variables: dependent variable = screening (yes response)	<i>N</i> = 459 Providers from three Northern California counties	Survey tool: attitude and knowledge on HCC screening. Questions on rationale for screening, test modality, and frequency Multivariate analysis Physician belief in reducing mortality with screening	Survey response rate = 61.8% Gastroenterologists (100%), internists (88.4%), family practitioners (84.2%), and nephrologists (75.0%) to screen for liver cancer in high-risk patients (<i>p</i> = 0.016) Screeners more likely than nonscreeners to believe	Conclusions: physicians screen due to fear of malpractice and quality control concerns. Total screening rate = 54.6% More research needed to evaluate screening efficacy, provider's reaction to lack of evidence, and better screening methods Limitations: providers sampled were limited to accessibility to

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
Compare the eligibility and tx rates of pts seen by GIs versus PCPs for CHB (V. G. Nguyen et al., 2015)	Design: retrospective descriptive chart review over 1 year Key variables: tx eligibility in group 1 and group 2 Tx initiation in group 1 and group 2	<i>N</i> = 402 pts Community clinics in the San Francisco Bay Area	299 pts managed by PCPs (group 1) and 1,103 pts managed by GIs (group 2) Eligibility rates in group 1 and group 2 by AASLD and U.S. Panel guidelines. Tx initiation rates in group 1 and group 2 Demographics a/w starting tx	screening reduced mortality and that not screening was a malpractice risk Screeners were more likely than nonscreeners to order any screening test if it was a quality of care measure (OR 4.39, CI 1.79-10.81) Pts less likely to be eligible for tx in group 2 GIs treated U.S. Panel-eligible pts more than PCPs. GIs were much more likely to initiate antiviral therapy in eligible patients than PCPs Predictors for tx: older age, male sex, higher ALT, and viral load Care at PCP clinic a predictor for no tx Failure to start tx due to normal ALT, pt loss at f/u, and refusal for tx	directories. Sample consisted of mainly Asian providers dealing with CHB. May skew results. Screening results high d/t bias of respondents and high proportion of CHB high-risk pts. No details on pilot-tested survey tool Conclusions: substantial number of pts not started on tx when indicated Physicians still rely on reported laboratory ranges or older literature as references for lab ranges Limitations: retrospective design and is not population based Notes: does not directly evaluate barriers

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				Provider knowledge—normal ALT as a reason for no tx suggests provider reliance on labs and old reference ranges	
Describe pt demographics, laboratory monitoring, and clinical parameters for CHB in regard to adherence to AASLD criteria (Sarkar et al., 2014)	Design: retrospective, cross-sectional, descriptive review of EMR from Northern California Kaiser Permanente Medical Care Program Key variables: pt characteristics, disease measures, HBV monitoring, and proportion of tx-eligible pts who were treated	<i>N</i> = 12,016 pt records from database of Northern California Kaiser Permanente in multispecialty clinics	Pt characteristics: demographics, comorbidities, and liver characteristics Disease measures: liver function by platelet count, liver panel, INR, viral replications (HBeAg, anti-HBe, and HBV DNA) tests, and coinfections HBV monitoring: ALT and hep B DNA testing every 6-12 months HBV tx: indications for tx: ALT > 1x ULN and hep B DNA > 20,000 IU/ml and/or HCC/cirrhosis with detectable DNA	Pt characteristics: 76% verified to be strict chronic HBV; the remainder inconsistent chronicity. Mean age = 49 years, with 51% men and 83% Asian. 70% were e-antigen negative and < 2% diagnosed with cirrhosis Disease measures: almost all pts tested for albumin, bilirubin, INR, and platelet counts. 80% tested for e-antigen status and hep C. Rate of testing for hep A, HIV, and hep D: 68%, 35%, and 12%, respectively HBV monitoring: < 14% had liver visit with specialist; 37% had f/u with PCP, and half had no visit. ALT and DNA levels performed < 40%;	Conclusions: only few pts (5%) in the untreated subgroup for CHB were indicated for tx initiation Laboratory testing for CHB pts not performed on a routine basis. Lab tests and HCC surveillance performed more often in a specialist setting. Most pts started on antiviral tx were eligible by criteria. PCPs had high rate of using lamivudine for tx for unknown reasons Limitations: retrospective study not generalizable to non-Kaiser pts. Lab tests may have been ordered for other purposes, overestimating this study's statistics Notes: results are in contrast to Zhang et al. (2012). Study shows no lack of adherence to tx initiation but lack of monitoring

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				<p>testing more common by specialist (90% vs. 47%)</p> <p>HBV tx: 5% of tx-eligible pts did not receive tx. 30% of untreated pts had recent lab testing. 17% of these pts were tx eligible. Specialist visits more likely to be treated (55% vs. 11%)</p>	labs
<p>Compare and contrast the recommendations from various societies. Address special populations (Skupsky & Hu, 2014)</p>	<p>Design: systematic review</p> <p>Key variables: HBV DNA and ALT in HBeAg positive and HBeAg negative pts per guideline</p>	<p><i>N</i> = not revealed</p> <p>Guidelines, systematic reviews</p>	<p>Lab levels, guideline recommendations, HCC screening, and tx</p>	<p>Varying ALT ULN per guideline</p> <p>APASL, EASL, and AASLD ALT 40, 31, and 30 U/L for men and 40, 19, and 19 U/L for women</p> <p>AASLD tx based on HBeAg status and liver bx results. EASL tx independent of HBeAg APASL d/c tx in HBeAg negative with undetectable HBV DNA. Keeffe et al.'s (2008) review emphasizes individualized pt tx</p> <p>HBV or starting immunosuppression—</p>	<p>Conclusions: discrepancies between guideline treatment criteria</p> <p>Many patients with CHB fall outside treatment guidelines</p> <p>Limitations: no details of how systematic review performed. Presents as a literature review without statistical analysis</p> <p>Notes: conglomerates all guidelines to discuss advantages and limitations. Addresses other relevant studies and reviews</p>

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				preemptive tx with NAs and monitor. Acute hep B—no treatment. Acute hep B with liver failure—start tx and consider transplant	
				Coinfected HCV, HDV, and HIV worse outcomes. Tx indications—same as mono-infection; caution resistance. HCV/HDV coinfection—tx focus for HCV and HDV surveillance. HDV coinfection aggressive—interferon tx is only tx	
Explore physician's adherence to hepatitis vaccination guidelines for chronic liver disease (Thudi, Yadav, Sweeney, & Behari, 2013)	Design: retrospective chart review of three time intervals Screening for HAV and HBV Vaccination rates	<i>N</i> = 705 pt records Center for Liver Diseases of the UPMC-Presbyterian Hospital	Screening rates in PCPs and specialists Rates of vaccination in each setting (PCPs and specialists) Pt demographics and disease characteristics	Screening rates by PCPs—14.5% and 17.7% Screening rates by specialists—76.7% and 74.0% Pt demographics and disease no influence on vaccination High variability among providers for vaccination	Conclusions: vaccination rates were suboptimal regardless of the setting Limitations: retrospective single-center study. Did not evaluate individual provider factors Notes: excluded study. Study excludes current CHB pts and does not evaluate vaccinations in this group of pts

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				practices (30%-98.6%)	
				Barriers to vaccination: three (1.2%) partial vaccination and 38 (14.7%) no vaccination d/t unclear reason or concurrent hydroxychloroquine and infliximab tx	
				Other reasons: vaccine unavailable, pt unaware where to vaccinate, no insurance, lost script, and no PCP	
Determine the extent of HCC and non-HCC liver-related deaths in patients who were excluded from tx based on the four current existing major guidelines (Tong, Hsu, Chang, & Blatt, 2011)	Longitudinal study Statistical analysis on descriptive data Quantify HCC or liver-related deaths Baseline labs (ALT, albumin, platelets, HBV DNA, genotypes, and mutation type recorded) Quantify tx-eligible	<i>N</i> = 369 pts from unrevealed database	Baseline labs = means and standard deviations EASL, U.S. Panel, AASLD, and APASL guideline tx criteria	30% of pts excluded from tx per guidelines died of non-HCC conditions and 53% developed HCC; 100% of these pts would be tx eligible with the use of impact score High HBV DNA levels a/w high risk of HCC who did not meet AASLD tx criteria	Conclusions: should monitor labs in pts defined as immune tolerant, inactive carriers, or cirrhotic with undetectable HBV DNA levels Treat if DNA > 2,000 IU/ml regardless of HBeAg status if necroinflammation or ALT > ULN. Cirrhotic and HBV DNA positive—start tx. Treat all pts with decompensated cirrhosis Pts in the gray zone or unable to bx should undergo risk impact score to diagnose

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
	pts when albumin, platelets, and precore/basal core promotor mutants included				necroinflammation Limitations: no evidence on risk impact score. Descriptive study. Small sample
Assess the attitudes and perceptions of PCPs in diagnosis and management of CHB in Asian American communities (Upadhyaya et al., 2010)	Design: cross-sectional descriptive analysis of two populations Phone questionnaire for randomly selected pts from an Asian American community Structured online questionnaire for randomly selected PCPs	<i>N</i> = 393 PCPs <i>N</i> = 610 pts from Asian American communities throughout the United States	Provider survey—guideline familiarity, attitudes, and indications for referral to specialists Pt survey—barriers to treatment	Respondents have some awareness regarding disease severity (66%). 30% of pts thought vaccines unnecessary. Lack of symptoms was a major barrier to testing (54%), followed by doctor's orders (21%) Most physicians (83%) found CHB serious and high prevalence in Asians. Low awareness of guidelines (62% unfamiliar); 31% familiar with AASLD guidelines PCPs referred to specialist in advanced disease (91%), rapid progression (89%), and resistant tx (85%) Patient barriers: fear of tx adverse effects. One in five belief herbal medicine	Conclusions: in primary care setting, need to educate pts and providers to increase awareness of disease severity Lack of familiarity to CHB guidelines by PCPs. Specialist referral in late stages of disease Suggests community-access programs to alleviate pt-provider culture and language differences Limitations: only three subgroups evaluated; not externally valid to all Asian Americans. Only pts listed in telephone directory included. Sample mostly women born domestically accessible by phone Notes: studies barriers by evaluating pt and provider perceptions. Doctor's orders is a large influence to management

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				<p>is better (distrust and unfamiliarity with Western medicine)</p> <p>Provider barriers: cost of tests, PCP belief disease stability does not warrant tests, and patient resistance were greatest barriers to disease monitoring and tx initiation</p>	
Evaluate the proportion of providers adhering to guidelines for screening immigrants for endemic conditions (Waldorf, Gill, & Crosby, 2014)	Design: randomized retrospective chart review Key variables: Screening per CDC guidelines Immunization per ACIP guidelines	<i>N</i> = 242 from electronic chart reviews in primary care clinics at Boston Medical Center	Screening: hep B screening (antibody and antigen). Purified protein derivative or interferon gamma release assay for tuberculosis Immunization: Vaccination if not immune to hep B	Screening: 43% of pts were screened for latent tuberculosis; 77% had f/u chest X-ray if positive for TB With latent TB testing, pts were five times more likely to be tested for HBsAg; 36% had HBsAg checked and 34% had HBsAb checked Immunization: 10% received hep A and/or B vaccine if not immune	Conclusions: there is a lack of screening and immunizations in primary care setting for CHB, TB, and other conditions Limitations: retrospective design. Small sample size with strict exclusion criteria limiting generalizability. Purely descriptive study performed only in primary care clinics Notes: only evaluates screening for CHB. Randomized study validates lack of adherence but does not evaluate the rationale
Evaluate adherence to HCC and identify predictors for adherence	Design: retrospective cohort study	<i>N</i> = 557 from community gastroenterology clinics in Northern	HCC screening categorized by: optimal, suboptimal, poor, and none	40.6% not screened appropriately or missed screening for HCC	Conclusions: frequent clinic visits a/w improved adherence. Routine visits improve adherence and clinical outcomes

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
(Wong et al., 2009)	Key variables: Screening modality, office visits, and appropriateness of screening method	California	Screening: serum alpha-fetoprotein, imaging, or both	Patients with more frequent visits to clinic were 3.4 times more likely to be screened	
Measure adherence to five areas of AASLD criteria; identify physician and pt factors contributing to nonadherence (Wu et al., 2014)	Design: retrospective descriptive review of medical records Key variables: Tx eligibility by AASLD criteria by five areas (ALT/viral load checks; liver bx; tx initiation; HCC screening; and HAV, HIV, and HCV coinfection testing) Predictors to guideline adherence	<i>N</i> = 962 from a database identified on Research Patient Data Registry at medical center and satellite health clinics	Eligibility: AASLD criteria by five areas: ALT/hep B DNA checks, liver bx if indicated, starting tx, HCC screening, and checking coinfection Predictors of adherence: physician type, pt demographics, and pt CHB disease phase analyzed on logistic regression models	Eligibility: ALT/DNA checks: 29% of pts. GI was 2.3 times more likely to check labs. Pt demographics not a predictor of physician adherence to lab checks Liver bx: 60% missed bx d/t physician nonadherence Tx initiation rate: 72% in eligible pts HCC screening: 45% not timely screened. Pts age > 45 7.45 times more likely screened. Inactive carriers and e-antigen negative more likely to be missed. Failure to order screening most common with non-GI, with much higher nonadherence Coinfection evaluation: 35% no hep A testing, 24%	Conclusions: poor adherence to AASLD criteria (liver bx to assess e-antigen negative disease, timely HCC and ALT monitoring, and coinfection testing). Providers were good at starting tx but poor at f/u. Missed bx d/t physician nonadherence Barriers to bx included provider and pt fear of complications. Provider nonadherence higher than pt nonadherence Unclear ownership of disease management (PCP or specialist) in inactive carriers led to no disease monitoring. Specialist referral process delays or missed referrals by PCPs d/t system issues unique to institution Limitations: retrospective study. Underestimates the difficulty of comprehending the guidelines. Barriers were identified but not

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
				no hep C testing, and 54% no HIV testing. ID more likely to screen hep C than specialties. Pts age < 45 were 2.05 times more likely for HIV testing than older pts	explored by the authors Notes: good study to identify barriers to tx and f/u. Suggests addressing knowledge gap, utilizing decision support tools (flags on EMR), and improving communication between providers
Define tx eligibility based on guidelines; determine the fraction of eligible pts who received tx; investigate predictors of tx eligibility and initiation of tx; and explore why eligible pts were untreated (Zhang et al., 2012)	Design: retrospective descriptive review of medical records Key variables: Tx eligibility based on U.S. Panel and AASLD eligibility criteria Tx status Predictors of tx eligibility and receiving tx	<i>N</i> = 612 from computer query for CHB. Medical record reviews were by a case report form from community-based GI clinics	Tx eligibility: U.S. Panel eligibility: ALT > 30 U/mL for males and > 19 U/mL for females and DNA > 2,000 IU/mL for e-antigen negative pts and > 20,000 IU/mL for e-antigen positive pts AASLD eligibility criteria: ALT > 60 U/mL for males and > 38 U/mL for females and hep B DNA > 20,000 IU/mL regardless of e-antigen status Tx status: lack of tx defined as no tx	Eligibility: 51% were eligible for tx. 53% were eligible per U.S. Panel criteria. 47% of these pts were also eligible per AASLD criteria Tx status: 29% by 12 months were treated per U.S. Panel criteria and 72% were treated per AASLD criteria. 50.5% of eligible pts remained untreated Predictors for tx eligibility: male gender, age, higher ALT levels, higher hep B DNA levels, and e-antigen positive Predictors for receiving tx:	Conclusions: nearly half of pts in a community-based setting were tx eligible by at least one guideline; only half of the number of pts were started on treatment within 1 year. Further research is needed to optimize tx Limitations: retrospective and with predominant Asian cohort not generalizable to other groups. More Asians infected with different clinical course. No tier model evaluation of care with this study focused on community setting Notes: identifies factors of lack of adherence specific to gastroenterologists. Delay for observation primary reason for failure to tx. Pt refusal only

Purpose (Author(s), year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements & Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Authors' Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
			started within 12 months f/u when eligible for tx by the U.S. Panel or AASLD criteria	older age and higher ALT levels	15%
			Predictors of tx: regression to calculate odds ratio relating predictors to tx eligibility and receiving tx	Reasons for no tx per U.S. Panel and AASLD, respectively: delay for observation (81%/56%), lost at f/u (30%/24%), pt refusal (15%/24%), no longer eligible for tx, financial concerns, pregnancy status, and other	

Note. AASLD = American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases, ACIP = Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices, AFP = alpha-fetoprotein, ALT = alanine aminotransferase, anti-HBe = hepatitis B e-antibody, APASL = Asian Pacific Association for the Study of Liver, a/w = associated with, bx = biopsy, CHB = chronic hepatitis B, d/t = due to, EASL = European Association for the Study of Liver, EMR = electronic medical record, FDA = Food and Drug Administration, f/u = follow-up, GI = gastrointestinal specialist, HAV = hepatitis A virus, HBeAg = hepatitis B e-antigen, HBsAg = hepatitis B surface antigen, HBsAb = hepatitis B surface antibody, HBV = hepatitis B virus, HCC = hepatocellular carcinoma, HCV = hepatitis C virus, HDV = hepatitis D virus, hep = hepatitis, hx = history, ID = infectious disease/HIV specialist, INR = international normalized ratio, lab = laboratory, med = medication, NAs = nucleos(t)ide analogues, PCP = primary care provider, PCR = polymerase chain reaction, QALYs = quality-adjusted life years, Rx = drug, TB = tuberculosis, tx = treatment, pt = patient, ULN = upper limit of normal, UPMC = University of Pittsburgh Medical Center, US = ultrasound. Table arranged in alphabetical order by first author's last name.

APPENDIX B

JOHNS HOPKINS EVIDENCE APPRAISAL TOOL

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix E: Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

Evidence Level and Quality:			
Article Title:		Number:	
Author(s):		Publication Date:	
Journal:			
Setting:		Sample (Composition & size):	
Does this evidence address my EBP question?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No Do not proceed with appraisal of this evidence
Level of Evidence (Study Design)			
A. Is this a report of a single research study? <i>If No, go to B.</i>		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
1. Was there an intervention?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
2. Was there a control group?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
3. Were study participants randomly assigned to the intervention and control groups?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
If Yes to all three, this is a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) or Experimental Study		<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL I	
If Yes to #1 and #2 and No to #3, OR Yes to #1 and No to #2 and #3, this is Quasi-Experimental (some degree of investigator control, some manipulation of an independent variable, lacks random assignment to groups, may have a control group)		<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL II	
If Yes to #1 only, OR No to #1, #2, and #3, this is Non-Experimental (no manipulation of independent variable, can be descriptive, comparative, or correlational, often uses secondary data) or Qualitative (exploratory in nature such as interviews or focus groups, a starting point for studies for which little research currently exists, has small sample sizes, may use results to design empirical studies)		<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL III	
NEXT, COMPLETE THE BOTTOM SECTION ON THE FOLLOWING PAGE, "STUDY FINDINGS THAT HELP YOU ANSWER THE EBP QUESTION"			

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix E: Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

B. Is this a summary of multiple research studies? <i>If No, go to Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Form.</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
1. Does it employ a comprehensive search strategy and rigorous appraisal method (Systematic Review)? <i>If No, use Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Tool; if Yes:</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
a. Does it combine and analyze results from the studies to generate a new statistic (effect size)? (Systematic review with meta-analysis)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
b. Does it analyze and synthesize concepts from qualitative studies? (Systematic review with meta-synthesis)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>If Yes to either a or b, go to #2B below.</i>		
2. For Systematic Reviews and Systematic Reviews with meta-analysis or meta-synthesis:		
a. Are all studies included RCTs?	<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL I	
b. Are the studies a combination of RCTs and quasi-experimental or ^ quasi-experimental only?	<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL II	
c. Are the studies a combination of RCTs, quasi-experimental and non-experimental or non-experimental only?	<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL III	
d. Are any or all of the included studies qualitative?	<input type="checkbox"/> LEVEL III	
COMPLETE THE NEXT SECTION, "STUDY FINDINGS THAT HELP YOU ANSWER THE EBP QUESTION"		
STUDY FINDINGS THAT HELP YOU ANSWER THE EBP QUESTION:		

NOW COMPLETE THE FOLLOWING PAGE, "QUALITY APPRAISAL OF RESEARCH STUDIES", AND ASSIGN A QUALITY SCORE TO YOUR ARTICLE

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix E: Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

Quality Appraisal of Research Studies			
• Does the researcher identify what is known and not known about the problem and how the study will address any gaps in knowledge?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Was the purpose of the study clearly presented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Was the literature review current (most sources within last 5 years or classic)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Was sample size sufficient based on study design and rationale?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• If there is a control group:			
◦ Were the characteristics and/or demographics similar in both the control and intervention groups?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
◦ If multiple settings were used, were the settings similar?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
◦ Were all groups equally treated except for the intervention group(s)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
• Are data collection methods described clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were the instruments reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.70$)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
• Was instrument validity discussed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
• If surveys/questionnaires were used, was the response rate > 25%?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
• Were the results presented clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• If tables were presented, was the narrative consistent with the table content?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> NA
• Were study limitations identified and addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were conclusions based on results?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
Quality Appraisal of Systematic Review with or without Meta-Analysis or Meta-Synthesis			
• Was the purpose of the systematic review clearly stated?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were reports comprehensive, with reproducible search strategy?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
◦ Key search terms stated	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
◦ Multiple databases searched and identified	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
◦ Inclusion and exclusion criteria stated	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Was there a flow diagram showing the number of studies eliminated at each level of review?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were details of included studies presented (design, sample, methods, results, outcomes, strengths and limitations)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were methods for appraising the strength of evidence (level and quality) described?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Were conclusions based on results?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
◦ Results were interpreted	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
◦ Conclusions flowed logically from the interpretation and systematic review question	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
• Did the systematic review include both a section addressing limitations and how they were addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	

QUALITY RATING BASED ON QUALITY APPRAISAL

- A High quality:** consistent, generalizable results; sufficient sample size for the study design; adequate control; definitive conclusions; consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence
- B Good quality:** reasonably consistent results; sufficient sample size for the study design; some control, and fairly definitive conclusions; reasonably consistent recommendations based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes some reference to scientific evidence
- C Low quality or major flaws:** little evidence with inconsistent results; insufficient sample size for the study design; conclusions cannot be drawn

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix F: Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

Evidence Level & Quality: _____

Article Title:		Number:	
Author(s):		Publication Date:	
Journal:			
Does this evidence address the EBP question?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No Do not proceed with appraisal of this evidence
<input type="checkbox"/> Clinical Practice Guidelines: Systematically developed recommendations from nationally recognized experts based on research evidence or expert consensus panel. LEVEL IV			
<input type="checkbox"/> Consensus or Position Statement: Systematically developed recommendations based on research and nationally recognized expert opinion that guides members of a professional organization in decision-making for an issue of concern. LEVEL IV			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the types of evidence included identified? • Were appropriate stakeholders involved in the development of recommendations? • Are groups to which recommendations apply and do not apply clearly stated? • Have potential biases been eliminated? • Were recommendations valid (reproducible search, expert consensus, independent review, current, and level of supporting evidence identified for each recommendation)? • Were the recommendations supported by evidence? • Are recommendations clear? 		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No
<input type="checkbox"/> Literature Review: Summary of published literature without systematic appraisal of evidence quality or strength. LEVEL V			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is subject matter to be reviewed clearly stated? • Is relevant, up-to-date literature included in the review (most sources within last 5 years or classic)? • Is there a meaningful analysis of the conclusions in the literature? • Are gaps in the literature identified? • Are recommendations made for future practice or study? 		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No
<input type="checkbox"/> Expert Opinion: Opinion of one or more individuals based on clinical expertise. LEVEL V			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has the individual published or presented on the topic? • Is author's opinion based on scientific evidence? • Is the author's opinion clearly stated? • Are potential biases acknowledged? 		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix F: Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

Organizational Experience:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Quality Improvement: Cyclical method to examine organization-specific processes at the local level. LEVEL V		
<input type="checkbox"/> Financial Evaluation: Economic evaluation that applies analytic techniques to identify, measure, and compare the cost and outcomes of two or more alternative programs or interventions. LEVEL V		
<input type="checkbox"/> Program Evaluation: Systematic assessment of the processes and/or outcomes of a program and can involve both quantitative and qualitative methods. LEVEL V		
Setting:	Sample (composition/size):	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Was the aim of the project clearly stated? • Was the method adequately described? • Were process or outcome measures identified? • Were results adequately described? • Was interpretation clear and appropriate? • Are components of cost/benefit analysis described? 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A
<input type="checkbox"/> Case Report: In-depth look at a person, group, or other social unit. LEVEL V		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the purpose of the case report clearly stated? • Is the case report clearly presented? • Are the findings of the case report supported by relevant theory or research? • Are the recommendations clearly stated and linked to the findings? 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No
Community Standard, Clinician Experience, or Consumer Preference		
<input type="checkbox"/> Community Standard: Current practice for comparable settings in the community LEVEL V		
<input type="checkbox"/> Clinician Experience: Knowledge gained through practice experience LEVEL V		
<input type="checkbox"/> Consumer Preference: Knowledge gained through life experience LEVEL V		
Information Source(s):	Number of Sources:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source of information has credible experience. • Opinions are clearly stated. • Identified practices are consistent. 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> N/A
Findings that help you answer the EBP question:		

**Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice
Appendix F: Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Tool**

<p>QUALITY RATING FOR CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINES, CONSENSUS OR POSITION STATEMENTS (LEVEL IV)</p> <p>A High quality: Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, private organization, or government agency; documentation of a systematic literature search strategy; consistent results with sufficient numbers of well-designed studies; criteria-based evaluation of overall scientific strength and quality of included studies and definitive conclusions; national expertise is clearly evident; developed or revised within the last 5 years.</p> <p>B Good quality: Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, private organization, or government agency; reasonably thorough and appropriate systematic literature search strategy; reasonably consistent results, sufficient numbers of well-designed studies; evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies with fairly definitive conclusions; national expertise is clearly evident; developed or revised within the last 5 years.</p> <p>C Low quality or major flaws: Material not sponsored by an official organization or agency; undefined, poorly defined, or limited literature search strategy; no evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies, insufficient evidence with inconsistent results, conclusions cannot be drawn; not revised within the last 5 years.</p>
<p>QUALITY RATING FOR ORGANIZATIONAL EXPERIENCE (LEVEL V)</p> <p>A High quality: Clear aims and objectives; consistent results across multiple settings; formal quality improvement or financial evaluation methods used; definitive conclusions; consistent recommendations with thorough reference to scientific evidence</p> <p>B Good quality: Clear aims and objectives; formal quality improvement or financial evaluation methods used; consistent results in a single setting; reasonably consistent recommendations with some reference to scientific evidence</p> <p>C Low quality or major flaws: Unclear or missing aims and objectives; inconsistent results; poorly defined quality improvement/financial analysis method; recommendations cannot be made</p>
<p>QUALITY RATING FOR LITERATURE REVIEW, EXPERT OPINION, COMMUNITY STANDARD, CLINICIAN EXPERIENCE, CONSUMER PREFERENCE (LEVEL V)</p> <p>A High quality: Expertise is clearly evident; draws definitive conclusions; provides scientific rationale; thought leader in the field</p> <p>B Good quality: Expertise appears to be credible; draws fairly definitive conclusions; provides logical argument for opinions</p> <p>C Low quality or major flaws: Expertise is not discernable or is dubious; conclusions cannot be drawn</p>

APPENDIX C

THEMATIC ANALYSIS OF INCLUDED STUDIES

Table B1

Barriers Categorized by Themes of the HBM With Recommendations

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
1	Burman et al. (2014)	PCPs Chart review	Prospective cross-sectional survey Retrospective descriptive review	Provider familiarity and knowledge lacking for HBV monitoring and HCC screening. PCPs' age negatively associated with screening rate Not screening for HCC a malpractice risk Knowledge and attitudes positive correlation Asian race and patient age a/w CHB monitoring Barriers: lack of resources (26%), guideline unawareness (25%), and unclear guidelines (25%)	Self-efficacy (familiarity, knowledge, unawareness, unclear) Modifying factors (provider age) Perceived benefits (avoid litigation) Perceived severity (pt race and age) Perceived barriers (resources)	Education for PCPs Clarify HCC screening methods and recommendations Promote guideline awareness Provide alternative resources
2	Ferrante, Clinton, Chen, and	PCPs	Prospective cross-sectional survey	Mean PCP knowledge score = 79%. Physicians managing six or more cases/year more	Self-efficacy (knowledge, familiarity, provider	Educate PCPs Recommend PCPs to refer

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
	de la Torre (2008)			<p>knowledgeable on CHB. Experienced (> 20 years)</p> <p>PCPs less knowledgeable on risk factors; 21% unaware of next step of management when HBsAg positive</p> <p>25% screened for HCC</p> <p>42% and 51% referred to specialists for chronic HBV</p> <p>No difference in PCP and practice characteristics</p>	<p>experience)</p> <p>Perceived susceptibility (HCC)</p> <p>Perceived severity (provider belief in disease severity)</p>	to specialist if managing less than six cases of CHB per year
3	Hearn et al. (2015)	HIV specialists and hepatologists (GIs)	<p>Prospective cross-sectional survey</p> <p>Retrospective database review</p>	IDs (36%) screened HCC and ordered routine labs less than GIs (81.8%). GIs more comfortable with CHB, but IDs more comfortable with coinfectd pts. Higher rates of HCC detection by GIs. Older age received less HCC screening	<p>Self-efficacy (knowledge)</p> <p>Perceived susceptibility (HCC risk)</p> <p>Perceived severity (pt age)</p>	Educate IDs on HCC screening
4	Juday et al. (2011)	<p>Inpatient and outpatient settings across the United States</p> <p>Pt healthcare claims</p>	<p>Retrospective descriptive cohort review</p> <p>Longitudinal</p>	<p>Poor adherence to guidelines for lab testing (ALT/viral load) for unclear reasons</p> <p>Predictors for lab monitoring: male and location</p> <p>Predictors for starting tx: higher viral load, males, and</p>	<p>Self-efficacy</p> <p>Perceived severity (sex/location)</p> <p>Perceived severity (labs, sex, disease burden)</p>	<p>Further research needed to evaluate cause of poor adherence</p> <p>Educate providers regarding risk factors</p>

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
				heavier disease burden		
5	Jung et al. (2010)	Los Angeles County Department of Health Services Pt database	Retrospective descriptive review Longitudinal	Males monitored more than females Northwest monitored more than Midwest (lack of screening programs) Predictors of starting tx: male sex, African American race, HIV coinfectd, previous liver bx, HBeAg status, viral count, younger age, lower albumin, longer duration of CHB, and frequency of visits. Providers of HIV pts were IDs with better tx adherence Asian race a/w not receiving tx Guideline published in 2002-2006 increased awareness	Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived severity (pt sex, variables, race, and age) Modifying factors (pt demographics)	Education to providers Promotion of additional programs Promulgate guidelines Refer to specialists
6	Khalili et al. (2011)	San Francisco healthcare system Providers	Prospective survey Cross-sectional study	More Asian population a/w provider adherence. No association with provider culture or language barrier Fear of malpractice	Self-efficacy (knowledge/unclear guidelines) Perceived benefits Perceived barriers	Provider education Clarify guidelines for HCC screening Premise for adherence

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
				<p>Perceived barriers: lack of resources, unclear guidelines, and financial barriers</p> <p>Factors a/w adherence: pts vaccinated, guideline awareness, provider < 40 years old, Asian pts, and higher provider knowledge scores</p>	<p>(resources, financial)</p> <p>Perceived susceptibility (Asian pts)</p>	Promotion programs for testing modalities
7	L. H. Kim et al. (2014)	<p>San Francisco health clinics</p> <p>Pt medical records from clinics (PCP and GI)</p>	<p>Retrospective descriptive review of medical records</p> <p>Multipoint data collection over 4 years</p>	<p>Low rate of adherence by PCPs</p> <p>Rationale for no tx: further observation, perceived normal ALT, and pt refusal (14%-27%)</p> <p>< 50% of tx-eligible pts were started tx in the PCP group. Seeing specialist a predictor for starting tx</p> <p>Gender disparity—females treated less frequently than males</p>	<p>Self-efficacy (knowledge)</p> <p>Perceived severity (observation)</p> <p>Perceived barriers (pt refusal)</p> <p>Modifying factors (pt sex)</p>	<p>Educate PCPs</p> <p>Refer to specialists</p>
8	Ku et al. (2013)	San Francisco Bay Area community multispecialty clinics	Retrospective descriptive review of case reports by 6 months	<p>PCPs less likely to check three main labs by 6 months compared to specialists</p> <p>Rationale for tx delay: delay for observation, pt refusal, and</p>	<p>Self-efficacy (knowledge)</p> <p>Perceived severity (observation)</p>	<p>Provider education on disease severity</p> <p>Refer to specialists</p> <p>Elucidate and simplify</p>

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
		Pt medical records		plans for pregnancy	Modifying factors (lifespan)	guidelines on labs (HBeAg, ALT, and HBV DNA)
9	T. T. Nguyen, Gildengorin, Truong, and McPhee (2007)	Three Northern California counties Multispecialty providers	Prospective descriptive survey Cross-sectional study	HCC screening due to fear of malpractice and quality control concerns Screeners more likely than nonscreeners to believe screening reduced mortality Equivocal evidence for benefits with screening	Perceived benefits Perceived susceptibility (HCC)	Provider education More research indicated
10	V. G. Nguyen et al. (2015)	Community San Francisco health clinics Pt medical records from PCPs and GIs	Retrospective descriptive chart review over 1 year	GIs started tx more often with more stringent criteria. Significant number of tx-eligible pts not started on tx Providers still reliant on lab reference ranges Barriers: difficult guidelines, guideline unawareness, and pt financial hardship Predictors for tx: older age, male sex, higher ALT, and viral load	Self-efficacy (knowledge, unclear guidelines, unawareness) Modifying factors (pt financial status) Perceived severity (pt age, sex, ALT, and viral load)	Elucidate and simplify guidelines Refer to specialists Promulgate guidelines Promotion programs
11	Sarkar et al. (2014)	Northern California Kaiser Permanente	Retrospective descriptive review of medical records Cross-sectional	Poor adherence to lab monitoring Specialists adhered more often	Self-efficacy (knowledge)	Provider education Refer to specialists Elucidate disease

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
		PCPs	study	<p>than PCPs</p> <p>Most pts on tx were eligible</p> <p>PCPs had high rate of using second-line tx agents</p>		monitoring and treatment guidelines
12	Upadhyaya et al. (2010)	<p>Asian American communities from numerous states</p> <p>Pts and PCPs</p>	<p>Prospective descriptive analysis of questionnaires and interviews</p> <p>Cross-sectional study</p>	<p>Low awareness of guidelines (62%) and unfamiliarity</p> <p>PCPs referred to specialist in advanced disease</p> <p>Patient barriers: fear of tx adverse effects and belief in herbal medicine</p> <p>Provider barriers: cost of tests, PCP false belief no monitoring needed in stable CHB, and pt resistance</p> <p>Lack of symptoms a major barrier (54%) to testing and failure by PCPs to order tests (21%)</p>	<p>Self-efficacy (knowledge/ unfamiliarity)</p> <p>Perceived barriers (pt resistance, cultural beliefs, financial)</p> <p>Perceived severity (lab stability, asymptomatic patient)</p>	<p>Provider education</p> <p>Promulgate guidelines</p> <p>Elucidate guidelines (labs to monitor)</p> <p>Refer to specialists</p> <p>Community outreach programs (as Upadhyaya et al. recommended)</p>
13	Wu et al. (2014)	Research Patient Data Registry at medical and satellite health clinics in the United	<p>Retrospective descriptive review of medical records</p> <p>Multipoint data collection over 1 year</p>	<p>Poor adherence to laboratory monitoring, liver bx, coinfection testing, and f/u after tx started. Non-GIs failed to screen for HCC</p> <p>Practice factors: orders not</p>	<p>Self-efficacy (knowledge, practice factors, system failure, unclear ownership)</p> <p>Perceived barriers (fear of complications)</p>	<p>Provider education</p> <p>Elucidate guidelines</p> <p>Refer to specialists</p> <p>Wu et al. (2014)</p>

No.	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design/ Intervention Time	Rationale/Barriers/Factors a/w Adherence	HBM Theme	Proposed Resolution
		States Pt records		carried out, missed referrals, system failure, and unclear ownership of disease manager Barriers: fear of complications from bx Provider nonadherence higher than pt nonadherence		recommends decision support tools and EMR reminders Consider novel noninvasive measures (Fibrosure, ultrasound elastography, risk impact score, etc.)
14	Zhang et al. (2012)	Chart review of community-based GI clinics linked to Stanford Medical Center Pt records	Retrospective descriptive analysis of medical records using two guidelines Multipoint data collection between April 2007 and February 2009	Predictors for receiving tx: older age and higher HBV DNA levels Rationale for no tx: observation (81%/56%), pt lost at f/u (30%/24%), pt refusal (15%/24%), and other reasons (AASLD and U.S. Panel, respectively) Half of pts eligible for tx and half received tx within 12 months	Perceived severity (pt age, viral load) Modifying factors (pt age) Perceived barriers (knowledge, pt resistance, loss, other) Self-efficacy (knowledge)	Provider education Promulgate guidelines Elucidate guidelines (labs to monitor) Refer to specialists Community outreach programs (as Upadhyaya et al. recommended)

Note. ALT = alanine transaminase, a/w = associated with, bx = biopsy, CHB = chronic hepatitis B, HBsAg = hepatitis B surface antigen, HBV = hepatitis B virus, HCC = hepatocellular carcinoma, EMR = electronic medical record, f/u = follow-up, GI = gastroenterology specialist, ID = infectious disease specialist, PCP = primary care provider, pt = patient, tx = treatment.

Table B2

Summary of Results: Cumulative Measures and Notes of Themes and Barriers

Authors (year)	HBM Theme	Comment	Main Theme/Notes
Burman et al. (2014)	Self-efficacy (familiarity, knowledge) Modifying factors (provider age) Perceived benefits (avoid litigation) Perceived severity (pt race and age) Self-efficacy (unawareness, unclear) Perceived barriers (resources)	7 barriers	Lack of self-efficacy main theme
Ferrante, Clinton, Chen, and de la Torre (2008)	Self-efficacy (knowledge, familiarity, provider experience) Perceived susceptibility (HCC) Perceived severity (provider belief in disease severity)	4 barriers	Provider knowledge inversely correlated with experience for HCC screening
Hearn et al. (2015)	Self-efficacy (knowledge) Self-efficacy (knowledge per specialists) Perceived susceptibility (HCC risk) Perceived severity (pt age)	4 barriers	Knowledge variance between specialties
Jung et al. (2010)	Perceived severity (pt sex) Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived severity (10 variables) Perceived susceptibility (10 variables) Perceived severity (pt race and age) Modifying factors (pt demographics)	15 barriers	Numerous variables influencing adherence to disease monitoring
Khalili et al. (2011)	Perceived benefits Perceived barriers (resources, financial) Self-efficacy (knowledge/unclear guidelines) Perceived susceptibility (Asian pts)	6 barriers	Provider-, practice-, and patient-specific barriers to HCC screening
L. H. Kim et al. (2014)	Perceived severity (observation) Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived barriers (pt refusal) Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived severity (observation) Modifying factors (pt sex)	6 barriers	Failure to start tx by primary care providers
Ku et al. (2013)	Self-efficacy (knowledge)	4 barriers	Failure to monitor and

Authors (year)	HBM Theme	Comment	Main Theme/Notes
	Perceived severity (observation) Modifying factors (pt refusal, lifespan)		start tx by PCPs Patient reluctance a major barrier
T. T. Nguyen, Gildengorin, Truong, and McPhee (2007)	Perceived benefits Perceived susceptibility (HCC)	3 barriers	Only study on provider beliefs and attitudes for HCC screening
V. G. Nguyen et al. (2015)	Self-efficacy (knowledge) Self-efficacy (unclear guidelines, unawareness) Modifying factors (pt financial status) Perceived severity (pt age, sex, ALT, and viral load)	8 barriers	Primarily guideline-specific barriers Patient-specific barriers
Sarkar et al. (2014)	Self-efficacy (knowledge)	1 barrier	Lack of efficacy in PCPs
Upadhyaya et al. (2010)	Self-efficacy (knowledge/unfamiliarity) Perceived barriers (pt resistance, cultural beliefs, financial) Perceived severity (lab stability) Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived severity (asymptomatic pt)	9 barriers	Patient cultural-specific barriers and provider barriers for nonadherence
Wu et al. (2014)	Self-efficacy (knowledge, practice factors) Self-efficacy (practice factors—orders, system failure, unclear ownership) Self-efficacy (knowledge) Perceived barriers (fear of complications)	7 barriers	Provider barriers more common than patient barriers for nonadherence to four guideline areas
Zhang et al. (2012)	Perceived severity (pt age, viral load) Modifying factors (pt age, viral load) Perceived barriers (knowledge, pt resistance, loss, other) Self-efficacy (knowledge)	9 barriers	Disease monitoring and tx barriers

Note. HCC = hepatocellular carcinoma, PCP = primary care physician, pt = patient, tx = treatment.